

PARLIAMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

**MARKET SHARE OF
THE FISHERIES,
FORESTRY,
TOURISM AND
WATER SECTORS.** ¹

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

South Africa has certain duties towards the international community as a signatory to the conventions and agreements arising from Agenda 21 at the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992, to ensure that all of its forests are sustainably developed and managed. South Africa has limited forests, and that forests in the broadest sense of the word, including plantations offer numerous benefits to adjacent communities and society at large. The natural forests of South Africa are the smallest of its seven biomes, covering less than 500 000 hectares (ha), which is much less than one per cent of its land surface. The South African forest sector makes a meaningful contribution to the economy of the country and has huge potential in the development of impoverished rural areas, which poses an enormous developmental challenge, a challenge that has not been successfully met by a great number of other developing countries.

Fish and fish products constitute a major source of income, food and recreation in the coastal communities. Fish products originate from two main modes of production: harvesting of wild fish (marine and freshwater) and aquaculture. The capture fishery is still the largest in terms of employment, landed tonnage and generated revenue, while aquaculture is very small and slowly growing. The fishing sector is facing a range of challenges such as climate change and over-fishing or illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing. For a developing country such as South Africa, exports of fish and fish products are among important foreign currency earner, particularly in Western Cape. The value of South African fish exports and imports have been growing steadily, despite being affected by the 2008 global financial crisis. Fish imports have also been growing steadily, however, South African remains a net exporter of fish and fishery products. The major contributors in the South African fish exports is the hake and abalone products which are mainly exported to the Western and Asian markets, respectively. Within South Africa, fish consumption remains very low and needs to change to stimulate local demand. For the fishing industry to remain sustainable and profitable, there is a need to improve on fisheries management, funding of research and development, expanding the current fisheries and investment in infrastructure for value addition and marketing.

Tourism plays a vital role in the South African economy. It has become one of the biggest contributing industries to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment in the world. In 2010 the South African Government identified tourism as one of the six core pillars of growth in its New Growth Plan featuring infrastructure development, the agricultural value chain, the mining value chain, the green economy and the manufacturing sector as the remaining five pillars. According to the new Industrial Policy Action Plan (IPAP2), tourism is acknowledged to be one of the areas expected to contribute towards development of rural areas by growing the economy and creating jobs. If this above mentioned rural development is to be achieved, all sectors of the tourism industry require expansion, in particular rural tourism; extreme poverty is predominantly located in rural areas. Agritourism can be seen as a subset of rural tourism. There is currently limited research on agritourism in South Africa due to agritourism being a relatively new concept. Various terminologies for agritourism

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include farm stays, agrotourism, farm tourism and farm based tourism, and these terminologies are furthermore used interchangeably in the literature.

Water is an integral part of the Agriculture, Fisheries, Forestry and Tourism sectors in so far as their operations, process and development are concerned. Their market share depends on water to a large extent. Agriculture is the major consumer of water in South Africa and in the world. As such if water diminishes in quality and quantity the Agricultural sector will shrink and ultimately cease to exist. The type of Agricultural activity that seems to be water intensive is the irrigation. Apart from irrigation livestock farming is also dependent on water – all agricultural activities are indirectly and directly linked to water consumption. Tourism sector is also directly and indirectly dependent on water irrespective of type. For instance game farming which is used for recreational hunting. The wildlife would require water for drinking and the tourist would also need water to bath, drink, cook and cleaning – all these activities are directly dependent on water as such availability of water determines the size and magnitude of the tourism's market share.

1 INTRODUCTION

The agriculture, forestry, fisheries, tourism and water sectors are crucial to South Africa's socio-economic development. However, the future of these sectors depend on critical issues such as climate change, population growth, skills shortages, changes in consumer needs and shifts in the global economy and related markets. The constant change in the supply-demand relations in the markets and trade requires a shift in the way governments operate. Government departments are responsible for creating an enabling environment to sustainably grow the mentioned sectors with a view of addressing socio-economic challenges, particularly, poverty, inequality and unemployment. The overall responsibilities include production and resource management, support services, trade and economic development, food safety and biosecurity, and infrastructure investments, diversification of products and services from the agriculture, forestry, fisheries and tourism.

The agriculture, forestry, fisheries and tourism's potential impact on empowerment and poverty relief is much larger than its actual weight in the economy. The impact is underestimated mainly due to inadequate information gathering and management, particularly, among smallholder producers, small and medium enterprises, and rural economies from the mentioned sectors. Combined, direct employment from the agriculture, forestry, fisheries and tourism sectors is in excess of 1.52 million and represent over 18 per cent country's gross domestic product (GDP).

The mentioned sectors contribute towards various Government Outcomes, which broadly relate to job creation, food security and rural development, natural resources management, regional integration and tourism growth; New Growth Path (NGP); the National Development Plan (NDP); the Medium Term Strategic Framework (MTSF) and the Industrial Policy Action Plan (IPAP). Targets between the national overarching policies vary considerably. Despite that anomaly, the National Development Plan argues that the four sectors have the potential to create an additional 1.45 million sustainable jobs. Each department is thus expected to develop policies and implementation plans to meet the 1.45 million additional jobs target. These sectors are some of Government's main priorities to ensure growth, transformation and sustainability of the South African economy.

The purpose of the report is to provide Members of Parliament with a review of economic contribution of the fisheries, tourism and water sectors. Where possible, selected emerging countries will be compared in terms of the various sectors. The report will reflect on the water sector being a strategic component of the agriculture, forestry, fisheries and tourism sectors. The report will conclude by making recommendations for consideration.

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2 MARKET SHARE OF THE FORESTRY SECTOR IN SOUTH AFRICA

– Dr S Watts

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This study set out to examine the status of the South African forestry sector, comprising the scope of the forest estate and its contribution to the South African economy. Consequently, it has been established that South Africa has never been rich in natural forests. Climate and the age-old effect of fires have confined natural forests to about 500 000 ha, which is less than one per cent of the country's land area. Natural forests have been depleted over the past three centuries. Nevertheless, much of the natural forest has survived, though currently there are reports of renewed forest destruction in some parts of the country.² South Africa has certain duties towards the international community as a signatory to the conventions and agreements arising from Agenda 21 at the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992, to ensure that all of its forests are sustainably developed and managed. It is in this respect that this study attempted to assess the market share of the forestry sector and its contribution to rural livelihoods and the myriad of uses and services that derive from natural forest landscapes. This is assessed in the context of existing key multilateral instruments, regional agreements that bear on the sustainability of forest resources and key national policy and legislation frameworks pertinent to the forestry sector. It has been determined that the three United Nations Conventions that derived from the Rio/Earth Summit have significantly contributed to shape South Africa's existing policy and legislation frameworks for the sector and other key national instruments that generally underpin environmental sustainability.

It is indeed affirmed that South Africa has limited forests, and that these forests in the broadest sense of the word, including plantations offer numerous benefits to adjacent communities and society at large. Such benefits include consumptive resources, spiritual and aesthetic needs, employment and ecological services such as carbon sequestration and water provision. However, in many situations access to such benefits is neither uniform nor equitable both between and within communities. In addition, forests and forest products add to the well-being and, at times, the very survival of millions of rural poor throughout the world. Such benefits are not restricted to rural people since many forest products are used and marketed within urban communities.³ However, the true magnitude and nature of the "dependence" on forests and forest products and services have not been fully assessed, as the current economic appraisal techniques fail to capture the true worth and usefulness of forest resources in a meaningful way to enhance the proper consideration and profiling of the sector, and hence its competitiveness. Conversely, the study confirms the forestry industry as truly competitive both in the domestic and international arena where South Africa has established a respectable presence among its peers as well as developed countries, particularly the G8+5.

The study proposes that Parliament, as an institution of public representations responsible for law-making and oversight should ensure that the current status of natural forests and forestry

² Ministry of Water Affairs and Forestry (1997).

³ Shackleton (2004).

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industry is determined, considering that the White Paper on Sustainable Forest Development in South Africa and the accompanying National Forests Act No 84 of 1998 are nearly 20 years in implementation, respectively. After all, it would be appropriate to determine what democracy means for the South African forestry sector, fundamentally in terms of realistic transformation. It is further suggested that Parliament should spearhead the initiation and institutionalisation of “Natural Capital Accounting” in South Africa to fully capture the true worth of the country’s forest resources; otherwise the sector would continue to occupy low profile on Government political agenda. There is a need to holistically account for all forest uses, encompassing consumptive and non-consumptive uses.

2.2 SCOPE OF FOREST RESOURCES

The natural forests of South Africa are the smallest of its seven biomes, covering less than 500 000 hectares (ha), which is much less than one per cent of its land surface. Notwithstanding, this biome has the highest diversity of plant species per unit area (e.g., comprising 418 species per ha compared to 98 species per ha for the Fynbos). Natural forest can therefore make an important contribution towards reaching national biodiversity conservation targets in prioritising areas for protection, and this is recognised in the conservation planning programmes of the Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF), South African National Biodiversity Institute and other national and provincial conservation agencies. These forests also play important roles in the environment as carbon sinks, in the functioning of water catchments, erosion control and providing resources on which the survival of many rural households depend. The forests and their settings are known for their beauty, and offer increasing potential for ecotourism, and non-consumptive livelihood opportunities for the poor. It is furthermore the most fragmented biome, consisting of more than 16 000 forest patches above the size of two ha of which the majority is less than 10 ha in size, thereby greatly increasing its vulnerability to human-induced impacts. These patches occur scattered in the high rainfall areas of the eastern parts of the country, from the northern border with Zimbabwe to the Cape Peninsula.⁴

It is important to note that South Africa’s forested landscape are the most densely populated, and the weight of human activities such as coastal development and harvesting of resources for commercial and subsistence use, place the forests under serious threat. It is in this respect that the National Forests Act No 84 of 1998, provides for the protection of the total natural forest biome. In contrast to the preceding statement, one observer stated that the majority of South Africa’s forest occurs on the lowland areas of the east coast, extending into the Drakensberg ranges. Forests that occur in this area are mainly broad-leaved evergreens with common species including *Olea capensis*, *Xymalos monospora* and *Podocarpus* species.⁵ Additionally, the country has extensive areas of woodland savanna, particularly in the Northern Province, Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal, where Acacias appear to be common species. *Colophospermum mopane* occurs in the Northern Province, while trees such as *Pterocarpus angolensis*, *Parinari curatellifolia*, *Terminalia* and *Combretum* species occur both in the Northern Province and in Mpumalanga. *Sclerocarya birrea* stretches from the Northern Province across Mpumalanga up to the northern parts of KwaZulu-Natal.⁶

⁴ Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF) (Undated).

⁵ Robertson (Undated).

⁶ Van Rooyen and Bredenkamp (1996); Granger (1996).

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According to DWAF, most demarcated conservation forests occur in the Eastern Cape followed hierarchically by the Western Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga and Northern Province⁸. In another report, the Department states that most natural forest occurs in the Eastern Cape, with about 140 000 ha and in KwaZulu-Natal that has approximately 91 200 ha. This is followed by the Western Cape that has about 60 000 ha, and by Mpumalanga and Northern Province, with 35 000 ha each.⁷ These contradict the above statement and also the following estimates of different categories of South African forests. What is clear is that South Africa has limited natural forest that occurs mainly along the eastern coast and requires innovative interventions to sustain it.

2.2.1 *Afromontane forest*

As the name implies, this is a forest type that occurs in mountain areas just below the tree line. It stretches along the mountain ranges from the Western Cape, mainly the Knysna area through KwaZulu-Natal to the Northern Province. Afromontane forests exhibit distinct layer of emergent and canopy trees that can attain a height of 30 or 40 m, and also show a distinct stratum of shrubs and herbs; and occupy approximately 596,300 ha. Trees in Afromontane forests include *Podocarpus latifolius*, *Podocarpus falcatus*, *Trichocladus ellipticus*, *Rhus chirendensis*, *Xymalos monospora* and *Ocotea bullata*, among others.⁸ South Africa's afromontane forests are floristically similar to other formations occurring throughout the continent.⁹

2.2.2 *Coastal forest*

There are 94,700 ha of coastal forest that occurs on a thin stretch of high dunes, especially along the Eastern Cape coast to KwaZulu-Natal, where it is well conserved. This forest type is also known as 'dune forest' by virtue of its occurrence. Common trees in coastal forest include Coast Red Miklwood, *mimusops caffra*; Natal Guarri *Euclea natalensis*, Cape Plane *Ochna arborea* and *Apodytes dimidiata*, among others.¹⁰ An important forest type within the same category is 'sand forest' which is restricted to the tropical and subtropical coastal belt of KwaZulu-Natal and occupies an estimated area of 34,500 ha. Sand forest is characterised by the dominance of deciduous and semi-deciduous trees in the canopy. There is dense tree stocking, with the upper canopy reaching up to 25 m. Characteristic species include *Cleistanthus schlechteri*, *Suregada zanzibariensis*, *Monodora junodii*, *Cadaba natalensis*, etc.¹¹

2.2.3 *Plantation forest*

It has been estimated that there are 965,000 ha of plantations.¹² However, the then Department of Water Affairs and Forestry (DWAF) states that industrial forests had grown to about 1.45 million ha by 1994, although the report confirms the pre-eminence of pines and eucalyptus in

⁷ DWAF (1996).

⁸ Low and Rebelo (1996); Lubke and McKenzie (1996).

⁹ Meadows (2000).

¹⁰ Low and Rebelo (1996); Lubke and McKenzie (1996).

¹¹ McKenzie (1996).

¹² FAO (1995).

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afforestation programmes. Accordingly, 56 per cent, 32 per cent and 11 per cent of the area had been planted to pines, eucalyptus and wattle. There are also 28 000 ha of small plantations of poplar which supplied wood for matches. South Africa's plantation forests are situated mainly in the Limpopo, Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal, and in the Eastern and Western Cape provinces, where favourable climatic conditions for tree growth exist. Quantitatively, Mpumalanga leads, with about 624 000 ha, followed by KwaZulu-Natal that has around 532 000 ha. Ironically, the most suitable areas for afforestation are also the most suitable for agriculture and conservation of biological resources.¹³

While there is no apparent consensus on the extent of South Africa's natural forests, it is clear that South Africa has limited natural forest resources. This had been described by a hard-nosed observer, who stated that the greater part of South Africa is "scarcely more clothed than the natives who inhabit it".¹⁴ However, the estimates of the Department agree on the extent of industrial plantations which have shown steady increases in recent years, particularly due to high demands for timber and other wood-based products from both domestic and foreign consumers.

2.3 UTILISATION OF FOREST RESOURCES

Forests are universally significant for their planetary functions, although their national values are frequently imputed only from their local economic and ecological functions. Forests are vital to the maintenance of a habitable biosphere – they conserve biological diversity; protect the earth's landscape from unexpected, sudden change; maintain the flow and quality of water in rivers and contribute in maintaining climatic stability, both at local and planetary levels.¹⁵ These functions have caused forestry problems, like other environmental issues to be analysed at the highest level, for example, the recent upsurge in summits which led to the signing of various conventions. These summits reflect global agenda-setting, although the *decision* to conserve forests, and the *capacity* and *will* to implement international forestry policy remain largely located within nation states. It is in this respect that international forestry agendas are expected to provoke nations into appraising the various functions and values of their forest resources. This thinking has led the South African Government to classify the importance of its forests into the categories described below.

2.3.1 Contribution to the GDP

The South African Government acknowledges that natural forests supply a wide range of goods and services, but rightly maintains that these are poorly understood. As a result, they are largely unaccounted for in national accounting books, although the commercial forestry sector GDP component has been put at about *two* per cent.¹⁶ The term *goods* refer to commodities which are directly consumed, while *services* include the non-consumptive uses provided by forest and woodland resources. Fuelwood, grazing, traditional medicine, curio industry and commercial timber are classic examples of forest goods. To this list non-timber forest products such as honey, bushmeat, mushrooms, edible insects, fibres and so on should be added. On the other

¹³ DWAf (1998).

¹⁴ King (1938:4).

¹⁵ WCFSD (1999).

¹⁶ DWAf (1995).

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hand, forest services include protection of biological diversity and water catchments, soil conservation services, aesthetics and ecotourism, and cultural and spiritual utility that forests provide.¹⁷

2.3.2 Forest products

About one-third of South African households rely on wood for energy, with as much as up to 80% of rural households depending entirely on fuelwood in some areas.¹⁸ As often, women trek long distances to gather fuelwood, and the average time spent in such a manner has conservatively been put at five hours per week. Approximately, 10 million tons of wood are burnt for fuel each year. About 6.0 million tons of this amount are extracted from natural forests. The quantity of wood consumed as household source of energy closely approximates that consumed in the formal industrial forestry sector which provides sales of about more than US\$160 million annually. Fuelwood accounts for nearly 10 per cent of net national energy consumption.¹⁹ It has been observed that fuelwood is the staple energy of the rural people, although it represents only 8.0 per cent of the energy supply. While this figure does not agree with the DWAF's estimate, a large proportion of the South African population depends on fuelwood. It has been estimated that 3.0 million households depend mainly on fuelwood for their cooking and heating. In some areas of the former homelands, there is a total dependence on fuelwood for energy, for example, in the Butterworth area of the former Transkei.²⁰

Fuelwood is an important forest and woodland ingredient in South Africa. Permitting its gathering from state and privately owned protected areas would add more value to these areas and contribute to the economic welfare of the neighbouring communities. Fuelwood has been noted as the most important secondary product in communal and protected areas; and computes its value for the central Mpumalanga lowveld conservatively at US\$6.5 million/annum.²¹ Recent case studies conducted on the consumption of secondary products in Bushbuckridge, Eastern Cape, and in two places each in KwaZulu-Natal and Northern Province indicate the average annual value of fuelwood at about US\$180 per household.²² With approximately 3.0 million households using fuelwood as a source of energy, and with many urbanites using the same resource for barbecue locally known as *braai*, it is plausible that the full contribution of natural forests to the energy sector has not fully been realised. This confirms DWAF's view that, although forests supply a variety of goods, they pass largely uncaptured by the existing resource valuation techniques which are biased in favour of commercial forest products.

South Africa's forests also supply structural materials such as poles and building materials; for example, in surveying indigenous tree uses in four areas in the Eastern Cape Province, it was found that many trees are vital for building materials and poles.²³ Furthermore, the above case

¹⁷ DWAF (1997).

¹⁸ DWAF (1996).

¹⁹ DWAF (1997).

²⁰ Ham and Theron (1999).

²¹ Shackleton (1996).

²² Shackleton *et al.* (2000).

²³ Van Eck (1997).

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studies indicate the mean annual value of poles at about US\$14/household, while the mean annual value of building materials for 'fences and pens' has been estimated at US\$18/household.²⁴ It is noteworthy that Shackleton and others have monetised many forest and woodland products, including carving wood, wood for tools and furniture, edible herbs and fruits, mushrooms, honey, thatch grass, weaving and construction reeds, medicinal herbs, insects, *inter alia*. However, it is cautioned that these values are rather conservative because they do not incorporate the value of products sold by producer or trading households. According to DWAF, forest-based medicinal plants employ approximately 225 000 healers; and the industry generates about US\$80 to US\$160 million/annum. This exceeds the number of formal employment in the forestry sector, although this figure hardly shapes public decisions on forestry.²⁵ It has been reported that about 19 500 tons of medicinal plants are traded each year in South Africa. In Durban alone, between 7 000 to 8 000 people are involved in gathering medicinal plants, with about 500 people undertaking the street trade. These estimates are expected to rise for the whole province of KwaZulu-Natal.²⁶

The curio industry which is heavily dependent on natural forests for wood, yields approximately US\$7.0 million annually. There are about 17 indigenous tree species, which are used in the woodcarving and furniture-making industry in the central Mpumalanga lowveld.²⁷ The value of the raw material has been estimated as at least US\$400 000/eight-year rotation cycle. Many woodland areas in the country provide fodder for livestock, whose value if accurately calculated would provide a better understanding of the importance of forest resources to this sector. Finally, the significant role of natural forests in supplying commercial timber and other species cannot be overemphasised.²⁸

2.3.3 Forest services

Natural forests and woodlands provide habitats for a wide range of fauna and flora, whose benefits to the South African economy and environment are indisputable, for example, the country's national parks and nature reserves that promote ecotourism. It has been estimated that around *five* per cent of South Africa's natural forests are in protected areas, such as national parks and nature reserves. Natural forests and woodlands contribute significantly to the maintenance of hydrological cycles. Forests are important types of land use as they protect the soil surface from erosion, in addition to maintaining soil fertility through leaf-fall and decomposition. Forest animal debris also enriches soil composition. It is noteworthy that many rural communities attach high spiritual and cultural values to individual trees, for example, the *Omumborombonga* tree or *Combretum imberbe* to which old Namibian legends trace the origin of human beings, cattle, sheep and various animals.²⁹ In the Mpumalanga Province, the fruit of *Kigelia africana* is believed to deter or neutralise lightning strikes, and as a result, people attach it onto their rooftops. Trees and forests shield human habitat and agricultural ecosystems from harsh environmental conditions. Furthermore, forests are essential for sequestering CO₂. It is

²⁴ Shackleton *et al.* (2000).

²⁵ DWAF (1997).

²⁶ Mander (1998).

²⁷ Shackleton (1996).

²⁸ DWAF (1997).

²⁹ Erkkilä and Siiskonen (1992).

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this function, which drew the world together to sign the United Nations Convention on Climate Change in 1992, or the commitments of the Kyoto Protocol in 1997. It is also the same role of forests among others that caused the world to protest against cattle ranching in Central America, and also against the construction of a 'highway' through the Amazon rainforests in the 1980s and early 1990s.

Although forest services are equally or even more important than forest products to certain segments of South African population, they too pass mainly unvalued. This is likely to constrain public investment in forestry, since decisions guiding such investments would be based on what the national accounting books indicate, which also fails to reflect the full value of forest consumables.

2.3.4 Employment

The most recent information for the purposes of the National Forestry Action Programme indicates that the industrial forestry employs the equivalent of about 61 000 full-time in the primary sector, i.e., growing and harvesting trees. An additional 50,000 are engaged in the secondary industrial sector, such as sawmilling, pulp and paper manufacturing, mining timber and poles and particleboard. Furthermore, there are about 50,000 people employed in the management of natural forests and woodlands.³⁰ However, the above estimates exclude employment in transportation services, such as that involved in bringing logs from forest to processing plants. Also unaccounted, for are seasonal labourers and those in the informal sector, for example, basketry, woodcarving, fuelwood and charcoal and *mopane* worm industries, bushmeat trade and so forth. The estimate that may enhance the public profile of the forestry sector is advanced by the Southern Africa Development Community (SADC), which indicates that the industrial forestry employs 242 000 people. This is equivalent to two per cent of the total economically active population. A recent survey at the DWAF indicates that lifeware in the forestry sector constitutes *two* per cent of the total economically active population, but puts the formal employment at 99 000 people, while the informal employment is portrayed at 30 000. The forestry sector employs explicitly a larger number of people both directly and indirectly than the official figures quoted here. Moreover, the Department conceded that "the many jobs involved in these sectors mean that over one million mainly rural people depend on this industry directly".³¹

2.4 INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENTS

The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), commonly known as the Earth Summit or the Rio Summit, held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil in 1992, represented one of the major steps forward in multilateral environmental agreements. The Rio Summit marked the first concerted attempt to link priorities for economic development with environmental protection under the rubric of "sustainable development". It was at the Rio Summit that a globally coordinated strategy for forests first emerged, resulting in producing a number of voluntary instruments that addressed forest management, including *Chapter 11 of Agenda 21* on human impacts on the environment, and the "Non-legally Binding Authoritative Statement of Principles for a Global Consensus on the Management, Conservation and Sustainable Development of All

³⁰ DWAF (1997).

³¹ DWAF (1995).

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Types of Forests”, popularly known as the “Forest Principles”. These guiding Principles set the stage for continued negotiations on forest arrangements. It was in this respect that the Intergovernmental Panel on Forest (IPF) was established in 1995 as an expert body under the auspices of the United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development with a mandate to analyse priority forest issues. The IPF was allotted a two-year term and an ambitious work program to combat deforestation and forest degradation. At the end of its two years, the IPF had created over 150 Proposals for Action (PFA) to address a wide range of global challenges to sustainable forestry.³²

It is important to note that three major global environmental conventions were also created around the same time as the IPF. All of these conventions contained mandates of direct relevance to forests. These multilateral agreements (housed within the UN) are the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (adopted in 1992 and entered in force in 1993); the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (adopted in 1992 and entered into force in 1994); and the UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) (adopted in 1994 and entered into force in 1996). The CBD is concerned with forests as habitat for a large number of the world’s plant and animal species. The UNFCCC recognises forests as carbon “sinks” capable of mitigating the effects of the human pollutants contributing to climate change. Finally, the UNCCD recognises the role of forests in preventing land degradation, desertification and drought. The UNCCD is worthy of special mention, considering that it was the first multilateral environmental agreement primarily driven by developing countries. Consequently, the IPF’s Proposals for Action call upon all of these global conventions to assist in the implementation of global priorities for forest protection.³³

Debate had continued regarding the need for a legally-binding agreement focused primarily on forests throughout this rapid development of multilateral environmental and trade agreements in the 1990s. As a result, a new expert body, the Intergovernmental Forum on Forests (IFF) was established under the auspices of the CSD to deal with many critical issues left unattended by the IPF, when the term of the IPF came to an end in 1997. That led to the reaching of an agreement on additional PfAs, bringing the total number of PfAs to 270, after three years of negotiations.³⁴ The IFF also proposed the terms of reference for a new international arrangement on forests through the CSD to the UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC). The ECOSOC went on to create the United Nations Forum on Forests (UNFF), thereby providing a more permanent home for the international dialogue on forests with a substantially higher level of political authority. The objective of the UNFF is to “promote the management, conservation and sustainable development of all types of forests and to strengthen long-term political commitment to this end”, to facilitate the implementation of forest-related agreements, and to foster a common understanding regarding sustainable forest management (SFM).³⁵

2.4.1 Regional Agreements

³² McDermott, C.L., O’Carroll, A. and Wood, P. (2007).

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Eastwood (2005).

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There are key regional legal instruments that shape forest management in South Africa, including the Southern African Development Community's (SADC) Forestry Protocol, established in 2002. The Congo Basin Forest Treaty, signed in 2005, represents Africa's first forest treaty. Important non-legally binding bodies in the region include the African Timber Association (ATO). The Africa Forest Law Enforcement and Governance initiative tackles challenges to forestry governance in Africa.³⁶ The SADC Protocol on Forestry of 2002 aims to promote the development, conservation, sustainable management and utilisation of all types of forest and trees; trade in forest products and achieve effective protection of the environment, and safeguard the interests of both the present and future generations. The Protocol was signed in Luanda, Angola, in August 2002, and entered into force in July 2009.³⁷

2.4.2 Key National Policy and Legislation Frameworks

The most important international instrument for sustainable forest management that has significantly influenced the South African forestry sector is the "Non-legally Binding Authoritative Statement of Principles for a Global Consensus on the Management, Conservation and Sustainable Development of All Types of Forests" that emanated from the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro, in June 1992. These principles reflect a first global consensus on forests and committed Parties to the prompt implementation of these principles. Countries also decided to keep them under assessment for their adequacy with regard to further international cooperation on forest issues. The Forest Principles regard forests as essential to economic development and the maintenance of all forms of life. For example, one of the principles, which states that "Appropriate measures should be taken to protect forests against harmful effects of pollution, including air-borne pollution, fires, pests and diseases, in order to maintain their full multiple value" appeared to have underpinned the existing South African legislation for the forestry sector. Similarly, the requirement that "Governments should promote and provide opportunities for the participation of interested parties, including local communities and indigenous people, industries, labour, non-governmental organisations and individuals, forest dwellers and women, in the development, implementation and planning of national forest policies," has been well-institutionalised in South Africa. The further requirement for governments to ensure "The full participation of women in all aspects of the management, conservation and sustainable development of forests..." is a key attribute of South Africa's forest legislation.³⁸

The Forestry Principles, have to a very significant degree, influenced the contents of the White Paper on Sustainable Forest Development and equally the National Forests Act No 84 of 1998 that descended from the Forest Policy (or the White Paper). The National Forests Act of 1998 is extremely comprehensive, translating what would have appeared vaguer in the policy into concrete or specific legal provisions. There are outstanding features of South Africa's Forests Act which if emulated in other southern African countries would protect the region's natural forests and woodlands. For example, in South Africa, the Government has the power to intervene to halt deforestation in any forest area within the borders of the Republic by declaring any forest that undergoes deforestation as controlled forest area. A violation of this directive is a second

³⁶ McDermott, C.L., O'Carroll, A. and Wood, P. (2007).

³⁷ SADC (2002).

³⁸ United Nations General Assembly (1992).

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category offence and carries a penalty of a fine or imprisonment for a period of up to two years, or both a fine and such imprisonment on a first conviction. Forest loss and degradation frequently occur and escalate without the knowledge of a country's competent authorities. To avoid running into this problem that has pervaded other African countries, the Government has mandated the DAFF to monitor forest resources; their biological diversity, health, vitality, productive functions, and their protective and environmental and social functions. The Department must also monitor the level of provision of socio-economic benefits; and the status and appropriateness of the policy and the legislative and institutional framework for forest management.³⁹

Another important feature of the Act is that the Minister can grant financial or other assistance to a registered landowner who has voluntarily agreed to have his/her land set aside as a *forest nature reserve*; a *forest wilderness area*; or *any other type of protected area*. This approaches the United States' wildlife habitat and forest incentives programmes or the European Union's set aside programme. Equally important is the absence of arbitrary reservation of protected areas, i.e., there is a legal provision for the Department to consult with the communities residing on the land adjoining the proposed protected area. To discourage illegal operations in state forests the law authorises any court that imposes a fine for an offence in terms of the National Forests Act to disburse a sum of not more than one-quarter of that fine to the person whose evidence led to the conviction or who helped bring the offender to justice. This would encourage local people to police state forests and woodlands. However, the negative aspect of this is that this benefit may not accrue to forest officers in the service of the state. Implicitly, they have no incentive to arrest offenders or would even accept bribes to look the other way unless there are administrative benefits associated with each offence successfully prosecuted, based on their evidence.⁴⁰

Thematically, the National Forests Act can be portrayed as a tripod. *Chapter 2* that deals with SFM, its criteria, indicators and standards; and emphasises the importance of research, monitoring and reporting forms the top of that tripod. One leg (*Chapter 3*) of the stool that supports SFM emphasises the "protection of forests and trees". Protection refers to the protection of natural forests, protected areas and trees against illegal activities and controlled forest areas. Another leg (*Chapter 4*) supporting SFM deals with the "use of forests"; this incorporates both non-consumptive and consumptive uses and collaborative forest management. Finally, the other leg of the sustainability stool is the enforcement of the Act (*Chapters 7 & 8*) that defines the offences and penalties; and assigns the responsibilities of forest officers.⁴¹

2.4.3 Key Sectoral Instruments Influencing SFM in South Africa

External policies and instruments also affect the sustainability of South Africa's forest resources. For example, South Africa's supreme law, the Constitution directs environmental conservation, while its overarching framework policy (the environmental management policy) provides a suitable framework for achieving forest conservation. This is adequately reflected in the integration of environmental management principles into the forestry policy and its implementation tool, the National Forests Act No 84 of 1998. Crosscutting policies, such as the

³⁹ Watts (2002).

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid.

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biodiversity and land policies, and the multilateral environmental agreements, such as the conventions on Biodiversity, Climate Change and to Combat Desertification also bear on forest conservation. This is practically illustrated by the South African biodiversity policy which mimics the parent document, and the Convention to Combat Desertification is well integrated into the forestry legislation and also into the environmental management policy. The current land reform programme, which does not regard land as agricultural capital only, but as landscape, as a component of ecological systems is considered an important intervention for biodiversity conservation, including forest.⁴²

Generally, there are synergies between South Africa's forestry policy and the policies governing water, energy, population, agriculture, tourism, macroeconomic and transport sectors. Optimisation of synergies with an aim to minimise negative effects between the forestry sector and the other sectors of the economy requires intersectoral policy co-ordination.⁴³ Intergovernmental co-ordination between national, provincial and local governments is also needed to harmonise forest use and management activities. However, South Africa's institutions tasked with this function are considered ineffectual, raising the concern that forest conservation is likely to be impacted by other activities that use land as a medium for establishment.⁴⁴

2.5 COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

The South African forest sector makes a meaningful contribution to the economy of the country and has huge potential in the development of impoverished rural areas, which poses an enormous developmental challenge, a challenge that has not been successfully met by a great number of other developing countries.⁴⁵ Plantations of indigenous trees such as the *Outeniqua* yellowwood may be economically more viable in terms of maintenance, wood value and water use than its commercial counterparts, as indicated in the study by the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR). When an economic measure for water-use efficiency was used, the southern Cape indigenous forests and a yellowwood plantation compared favourably, with exotic plantations. The improved performance of the indigenous systems based on economic criteria is because they have lower maintenance costs with substantially larger product prices. Also, levelling benefits and costs ensures that systems with large upfront costs and long rotations, typical of stands of indigenous trees, can be compared with shorter-rotation plantations and not unfairly selected against. In addition, further economic benefits from indigenous plantations may be gained from by-products such as traditional medicine, fruits, recreation, climate-change mitigation through carbon storage and tourism.⁴⁶

However, the well-established forestry industrial sector in South Africa is largely focused on short-rotation exotic plantations. The sector is largely structured geographically around the location of timber resources, although significant beneficiation also occurs around urban centres in Gauteng and the Western provinces. Envisioned expansion of afforestation in the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal will potentially play a critical role in those provinces rural development.

⁴² Watts (2001).

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Watts (2006).

⁴⁵ Ngcobo (2002).

⁴⁶ Dye (2008).

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The sustainable growth of timber inputs is critical to the future of the wood, pulp (WPP) sector's competitiveness. The paper and pulp sector has clearly established competitive advantage and a coherent policy supported by skills development to ensure this competitiveness is sustained. Similarly, there are relatively large firms in primary processing and secondary beneficiation sector that are well-positioned competitively for the near future. There are a multitude of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the sector whose existence appears to be tenuous with prospects of either marginalised subsistence or withdrawal being likely for many of these firms. This uncertainty around the future for the SMEs comes from uncertainties around timber supplies and the system of skills development.⁴⁷

Despite these concerns the sector has benefited from a large rise in domestic demand in recent years. Domestic demand for products from the WPP sector therefore represents a real competitive advantage for many domestic producers. However, competition from abroad continues to grow especially as other countries with similarly favourable growing environments facilitate export promotion. A critical challenge facing the sector is its ability to produce the necessary timber supplies for primary processing and secondary beneficiation. Directly linked to the supply of timber is the competitive advantage of companies in the WPP sector. Without competitively priced timber inputs, a substantial competitive advantage of the sector will be lost. Transformation of skills levels in the paper and pulp sector is another key aspect of the sector's challenge to ensure competitiveness in the future. Increasing knowledge intensity of the workforce has therefore become a critical priority within the sector. A challenge identified in training the workforce to enhance its skills is the outcomes based learning approach. This approach requires mentorship which is resisted within the workforce and adds considerable work to translate the existing curriculum. The uptake of learnership opportunities has therefore been constrained.⁴⁸

2.6 RECOMMENDATIONS AND ROLE FOR PARLIAMENT

- Parliament should ensure determining the changes in the forestry sector in the past 20 years. For example, have natural forests increased or receded and why? A similar determination should be made for industrial (plantation) forestry.
- Parliament should facilitate the Department (DAFF) to calculate the total economic value of natural forest resources and further determine the number and success of community forest agreement (between state, as represented by the Department and local communities).
- Parliament should determine the profile of the ownership of South Africa's forestry industry to determine 'who are the shareholders of the 400 or more companies, which have invested in forestry', and whether adequate transformation has indeed taken place in the sector.
- Parliament should determine the ownership and status of woodlands in South Africa, and further assess the impact of the current ownership on the sustainability of woodland resources in the Republic, particularly in communal areas.

⁴⁷ Pogue (2008).

⁴⁸ Ibid.

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3 MARKET SHARE OF THE FISHERIES SECTOR IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN ECONOMY

- Mr Joseph Ginindza

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Fish⁴⁹ is among the most traded food commodities worldwide. Fishery trade has expanded considerably in recent decades, as the fisheries sector operates in an increasingly globalised environment. The way fishery products are prepared, marketed and delivered to consumers has changed significantly, and commodities may well cross national boundaries several times before final consumption. Fish can be produced in one country, processed in a second and consumed in a third. Among the driving forces behind this globalised fisheries and aquaculture value chain are: decreases in transport and communication costs; outsourcing of processing to countries where comparatively low wages and production costs provide a competitive advantage; increasing consumption of fishery commodities; favourable trade liberalization policies; more efficient distribution and marketing; and continuing technological innovations, including improvements in processing, packaging and transportation. All these factors have facilitated and increased the movement of production from local consumption to international markets.⁵⁰

Fish products are essential to food security, providing over 1 billion people with their main source of protein and more than 4.3 billion people with about 15 per cent of their average per capita animal protein intake.⁵¹ Fish proteins are particularly important for preschool-aged children and pregnant women. World fish resources also have a key role in maintaining and expanding employment levels. Over 140 countries have marine fisheries that provide employment for local and foreign workers. In 2010, wild fisheries and aquaculture provided incomes and livelihoods for an estimated 54.8 million people engaged in the primary sector of fish production. Artisanal fisheries, or small-scale near-shore fishing, comprise 90 per cent of all fishing jobs worldwide, approximately 45 per cent of the world's fisheries and nearly 25 per cent of the world's catch. Apart from the primary production sector, fisheries and aquaculture provide numerous jobs across the supply chains, in activities such as processing, packaging, marketing and distribution, manufacturing of fish-processing equipment, net and gear making, ice production and supply, boat construction and maintenance, management, research and administration. This is estimated to support the livelihoods of 660 to 820 million people, or 10 to 12 per cent of the world's population.⁵²

⁴⁹ The term "fish" indicates fish, crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic animals, but excludes aquatic mammals, crocodiles, caimans, alligators and aquatic plants.

⁵⁰ Lee et al., 2012; Macfadyen & Allison (2009).

⁵¹ FAO (2012);

⁵² FAO (2014b); International Labour Organization (2015); United Nations Environment Programme (2013).

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The South African fisheries sector is divided into marine and inland fisheries, which are further divided into capture, aquaculture and, to a lesser extent, culture⁵³ fisheries. The capture fishery is subdivided into commercial, sport and recreational, and subsistence or small-scale fisheries. The marine fisheries are more developed and have structured regulatory and legislative instruments, while inland fisheries is underdeveloped and has fragmented legislative instruments.⁵⁴ Fisheries play a crucial role in terms of jobs, livelihood and sustainability in many the coastal and inland communities. The sport and recreational fishing (inland and marine) has approximately 2.5 million participants annually, translating to over R18 billion worth of direct and indirect economic impact in terms of jobs, salaries and businesses.⁵⁵ Estimating the total value and impact of the commercial fishery (marine and inland) is difficult to estimate due to short-comings, mainly, in the inland commercial fishing sector such as limited access to resources, low demand for freshwater fish, the lack of an inland fisheries policy, unclear fisheries management objectives and being the scarcity and outdated nature of the information. The marine commercial fishing industry currently employs approximately 27 000 people directly and approximately 100 000 indirectly and is valued at approximately R6 billion annually.⁵⁶ However, there are more than 7 300 subsistence and small-scale fishers in 137 marine fishing communities of which approximately 53 per cent are food insecure. Employment figures and value of freshwater aquaculture is scarce and poorly documented, however, marine aquaculture employs more than 1 600 permanent employees and is valued at R379 million.⁵⁷

This paper highlights the economic contribution of the fisheries sector, reflect on trends and changes in the market and regulatory environment, and conclude by assessing the challenges and make recommendations.

3.2 TRENDS AND CHANGES IN MARKETS

Fishery trade is closely tied to the overall economic state both nationally and internationally. Since 2009, the world economy has entered a difficult phase characterised by significant downside risks and fragility, with great uncertainty on how markets will evolve in the medium term. World trade has been hit by a series of economic, financial and food crises. At present, the global economy appears to be transitioning towards more stable but slower growth. Economic conditions are rebounding in both developed and developing economies, but the revival in both trade and output remains slower in developed countries. After a difficult 2009, characterised by a sharp decline of fish prices and a contraction in demand and trade, the seafood sector expanded again in 2010 and early 2011. This recovery was partly due to higher average fish prices as well as to growing demand. Consumer demand has been particularly strong in developing countries supported by the faster than expected

⁵³ Culture fishery refers to the release of seeds or juveniles into the wild environment to be harvested later or for simply stock enhancement.

⁵⁴ Marine Living Resources Act, 1998 (Act No. 18 of 1998); McCafferty et al., (2012).

⁵⁵ Leibold & Van Zyl (2008).

⁵⁶ McCafferty et al. (2012); Department of Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries (2012a).

⁵⁷ Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (2012a, 2013a); McCord & Zweig (2011).

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economic upturn. According to the World Bank, five years after the global financial crisis, the world economy is showing signs of bouncing back in 2014. South Africa, as one of the developing countries, is also firming partly due to the recovery in high-income economies as well as moderating, but still strong, growth in China.⁵⁸

3.2.1 Global production

The globally increasing demand for seafood combined with maximally exploited capture fisheries has resulted in a rapid expansion of aquaculture production to alleviate this supply deficit. The global fisheries production (fish, aquatic plants and non-food products) from capture and aquaculture grew from 172.7 million tonnes in 2011 to 181.7 million tonnes in 2012. The 2012 total aquaculture production (fish, aquatic plants and non-food products) was 90.4 million tonnes, having grown from 79 million tonnes in 2010 and continues to grow, albeit at slower rate (6.2 per cent per annum in the period between 2000 and 2012).⁵⁹ Capture fisheries have stagnated around 91 million tonnes per annum. In 2012, aquaculture contributed 49 per cent of the total food fish and is now on track to be the main source of fish in the near future. Global fish production has grown steadily in the last five decades, with food fish supply increasing at an average annual rate of 3.2 per cent, outpacing world population growth at 1.6 per cent. The total fish production varies on country basis (Figure 1), mainly as a result of the state of the ecosystem and management of aquaculture and capture fisheries.

Figure 1. Total fish production by country during 2012 (GlobeFish, 2014)

⁵⁸ FAO (2014); OECD-FAO (2011).

⁵⁹ FAO (2012, 2014b).

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Aquaculture production is now more of a priority in order to meet the growing demand of fisheries products. Asia is leading in aquaculture production accounting for 88 per cent of the 2012 global aquaculture production while Africa contributed 2.2 per cent. Over the past decade, aquaculture in Africa grew from 1.2 per cent to 2.2 per cent, mainly as a result of development of freshwater aquaculture. Egypt contributed 69 per cent percent of Africa's aquaculture production in 2012 and this trend is likely to be maintained. In terms of top producers in Africa, South Africa slipped from being ranked number 6 in 2000 to number 10 in 2010. Fisheries production in South Africa is still dominated by the capture fisheries having contributed more than 705 000 tonnes in 2012, of which aquaculture only contributed 6 000 tonnes.⁶⁰

3.2.2 South African fish trade

Fish and fish products are an increasingly popular item on consumers' plates because of being an important source of nutrients required for healthy growth. In developed countries, it is a premium protein source and in many developing countries it is among the main ones. Globally, fish provide just under 3 billion people with almost 20 per cent of their animal protein intake. Based on this current picture, key emerging issues around the future of fisheries trade include: the prospect for aquaculture; the sustainable management of capture fisheries; whether sustainability certification can address public concerns regarding fisheries and aquaculture; and how to curb illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing. Trade is an important factor across each of these.⁶¹ For developing countries, such as South Africa, exports of fish and fish products are among important foreign currency earner. The major contributors in the South African fish exports is the hake and abalone products which are mainly exported to the Western and Asian markets, respectively. The Asian markets are increasingly becoming the most important for the growing aquaculture sector.

The value of South African fish exports and imports have been growing steadily (Figure 2), despite being affected by the 2008 global financial crisis. Fisheries exports grew from R3.2 billion in 2009 to R3.5 billion in 2012, which translates to 9.7 per cent growth and still remains at the positive territory, despite growing at a mere 1 per cent between 2011 and 2012. Fish imports also experienced growth during the same period, growing from R834 million to R1.1 billion which translates to a 26 per cent growth. The trade balance remained on the positive territory for 10 consecutive years. There is a sign that the trade balance is improving gradually – growing at 3.9 per cent between 2009 and 2012. It is, however, concerning that during the 2009-2012 period, the country's fishery import value grew by 26 per cent.

⁶⁰ FAO (2012, 2014b); FAO Fishstat Plus (2013).

⁶¹ FAO (2014b); Department of Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries (2012b); Wesgro (2014).

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Figure 2. South African trade in fish and fisheries products between 2003 and 2012 (Wesgro, 2014)

Spain was South Africa's largest fish export market in 2012 accounting for fish worth R623.1 million, followed by Hong Kong and Italy at R488.9 million R478 million, respectively (Figure 3). Exports to Spain, Hong Kong and Italy accounted for 17.5 per cent, 13.8 per cent and 13.4 per cent, respectively. Angola was South Africa's largest and strongest growing African market, importing fish to the value of R87.5 million. The top 10 fish export destinations accounted for 77 per cent of the total fish exports in 2012. The top exported fish product from South Africa was fish fillets, fish meat, mince except liver, roe with an export value of R665.4 million. Exports of this good accounted for 19 per cent of all fish exports from South Africa. Exports of cuttle fish, squid (frozen, dried, salted or in brine) was the second largest export at R389.1 million, followed by rock lobster and other sea crawfish (not frozen) at R318.1 million.

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Figure 3. The top 10 markets for fish exported by South Africa during 2012 (Wesgro, 2014).

South Africa imported 25 per cent of all its fish from India (R267.6 million) in 2012, followed by imports from Norway (R134.2 million) and China (R101.7 million), with Mozambique (R46.6 million) being South Africa's largest African import market (Figure 4). Spain, Falkland's islands and Norway were the fastest growing import markets. South Africa imported frozen shrimps and prawns to the value of R317.4 million in 2012 with this being the Republic's top fish import. Cuttle fish, squid (frozen, dried, salted or in brine) (R166.7 million) and frozen fish (R119.1 million), were South Africa's second and third largest import products respectively. At provincial level, the Western Cape is the leading fish catchment and producing province in South Africa and accounted for 85 per cent of all fish exports from the country. Fish trade hit its peak in 2008, with the province recording its largest trade surplus. In 2012, fish export and imports both declined by 0.32 per cent and 3.55 per cent respectively, due to the larger decrease in imports. During the same period, the Western Cape improved its trade balance by 0.96 per cent. The province has consistently maintained a trade surplus in the 10-year period analysed.

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Figure 4. The top 10 markets for fish imported by South Africa during 2012 (Wesgro, 2014)

3.2.3 Fish consumption

The proportion of fisheries production used for direct human consumption increased from about 71 per cent in the 1980s to more than 86 per cent (136 million tonnes) in 2012, with the remainder (21.7 million tonnes) destined to non-food uses such as fishmeal and fish oil production. Global fisheries continue to set new records, particularly, aquaculture. Production has risen to new levels as a result of aquaculture, which is fast approaching 50 per cent in its contribution of fish for human consumption. The world fish consumption has increased from 18.9 kg in 2010 to a new record of 19.2 kg per capita according to the preliminary estimates of 2012, and as of 2014, trade is in excess of US\$130 billion. Freshwater fish and diadromous fish lead in terms of consumed fish (6.7 kg per year), followed by pelagic and demersal fish at 3.2 and 2.9 kg per year, respectively.⁶²

Despite the overall increase in the availability of fish to most consumers, growth patterns of per capita apparent fish consumption have been uneven. For example, it has remained static or decreased in some countries in sub-Saharan Africa (e.g. the Congo, Gabon, Liberia, Malawi and South Africa) and, albeit from a high level, in Japan in the last two decades, while growing most substantially in East Asia (from 10.7 kg in 1961 to 35.4 kg in 2010), Southeast Asia (from 12.8 to 33.4 kg) and North Africa (from 2.8 to 12.2 kg). China has been responsible for most of the growth in world per capita fish availability (89.8 million tonnes), owing to the dramatic expansion in its fish production, in particular from aquaculture. The EU, USA and Japan are the main fish importers, however, the importance of the Russian Federation as a fish importing country is growing steadily. The driving force behind this impressive surge has been a

⁶² FAO (2014a, b)

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combination of population growth, rising incomes, and urbanization interlinked to the strong expansion of fish production and modern distribution channels.⁶³

In 2011, the human population of South Africa was approximately 52 million, and is slowly growing at 1 per cent per year. If the economy continues at current growth rate, the population is expected to grow to 58.5 million by 2030. Food production or imports and accessibility must increase to feed the expanding population, and production needs to increase using the shrinking or unstable natural resources. In addition, the demand for certain food types will shift as more people become wealthier. There is an observed shift from staple grain crops to a more diverse diet. South Africans have shown a decrease in the consumption of the staples maize and bread, and have massively increased their annual consumption of chicken from 6 kg to 27 kg per person. Per capita egg consumption has also doubled. The per capita consumption of fruit and vegetables has remained constant, while beef, mutton, pork and milk consumption has declined. Fish consumption is on the increase, albeit, very slow. In 2011, South African fish consumption per capita was only 5.7 kg and 5 per cent of total animal protein. The South African fish consumption is below the African fish consumption level of 9.7 kg per person.⁶⁴

Figure 5. Total fish consumption by country during 2012 (GlobeFish, 2014).

3.3 INTERNATIONAL TRADING FRAMEWORKS

The amount of regulatory information or policies affecting trade in fishery products is vast and often dispersed and organised under various organisations. The nature in which the information is organised is often seen as the source of difficulty in trade on

⁶³ FAO (2014b)

⁶⁴ FAO (2014b); Goldblatt (2010); National Planning Commission (2012).

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fish and fish products because without internet access to such information it is almost impossible to tick all the boxes. There are several aspects that affect market access and competitiveness of South African fisheries exports to the EU, USA and Asian countries - the main end-market. This section will briefly highlight institutions shaping the regulatory framework on trade in fishery products. The relevance of the regulatory frameworks range from being general policy framework, specific to geographic area, institution, to policy of the institution and commodity. On a global level, the World Trade Organisation (WTO) and the organisations of the United Nations (UN) system are the main actors shaping the regulatory framework on trade in fishery products. The WTO provides the institutional structure for the opening of world markets, whereas UN organisations address the issues of sustainable development, environmental conservation and food security as targets world trade liberalisation must meet. The WTO system is based on a series of agreements whose aim is the gradual opening of international markets in goods, with the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), services, with the General Agreement on Trade in Services and traded inventions, with the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights.⁶⁵

During the 1994 Uruguay Round, fisheries were left out of the Agreement on Agriculture at the insistence of some EU countries that benefited from the EU fisheries subsidy regime. As a result, fisheries-related issues are covered by various other agreements. Most notably, fisheries subsidies fall under the discipline of the Agreement on Subsidies and Countervailing Measures. The main areas up for negotiation in the Doha Round are tariff and non-tariff barrier reductions under the negotiating group on Non-Agricultural Market Access and specific mention of a reduction of fisheries subsidies under the WTO negotiating 'Group on Rules'. As for the EU, the Cotonou Agreement applies to all African members that are part of the African Caribbean Pacific group of countries. This agreement provides tariff-free access to the EU provided that fish exports comply with specific Rules of Origin. If ROO fail, then a country has to export to the EU under the higher Most-Favoured-Nation tariff rates.⁶⁶

International NGOs have a strong influence on the shaping of the regulatory framework of trade in fishery products. Some NGOs lobby the WTO and UN agencies to raise the profile of the environment, sustainable development and food safety in their trade agendas. Organizations such as the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) set up practical tools such as eco-labelling schemes to foster sustainable trade in fishery products. The South African hake is one such certified by the MSC, and other species are in the process of being certified as ecologically sustainable. Within South Africa, an institution such as the Southern African Sustainable Seafood Initiative in partnership with the World Wildlife Fund increases the awareness of seafood consumers around different species of fish, to discourage them from choosing illegal and unsustainable species, and to guide them towards more ocean-friendly choices when faced with a selection of different species. To this effect, three colour codes (red, orange and green)

⁶⁵ Shortte (2013).

⁶⁶ Hezekiah (2001); Ponte et al., (2005).

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were developed. The red group includes unsustainable species as well as those that are illegal to sell in South Africa. Fish in this category are never to be bought. An orange group includes species that have associated reasons for concern and consumers should be cautious when choosing any of these species. The green-listed species are the best choice because it contains species that are best managed, most sustainable and available to consumers.⁶⁷

Non-tariff measures are generally defined as policy measures other than ordinary customs tariffs that can potentially have an economic effect on international trade in goods, changing quantities traded, or prices or both. Non-tariff measures are further divided into sections, the technical measures, the non-technical measures and exports. The fisheries sector is mainly affected by Chapter A under the non-technical measures which deals with sanitary and phytosanitary measures (generally referred to as SPS). SPS gathers measures such as restriction for substances and ensuring food safety, and those for preventing dissemination of disease or pests. Chapter A also includes all conformity-assessment measures related to food safety, such as certification, testing and inspection, and quarantine. The SPS are implemented through prohibition and/or restriction of the final products to be imported. The Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT), also a non-tariff measure, tries to ensure that technical standards, regulations and conformity assessment procedures do not create unnecessary barriers to trade. Countries can adopt standards they deem appropriate for human, animal or plant health, protection of the environment or of consumers. However, WTO promotes the use of international standards and discourages methods giving to domestic goods an unfair advantage.⁶⁸

The prominent Fisheries Partnership Agreements (FPAs) between EU and African Caribbean Pacific (ACP) countries in fisheries are the:⁶⁹

- Development cooperation programmes in the fisheries sector under the Cotonou Partnership Agreement;
- Bilateral fisheries agreements under the international part of the Common Fisheries Policy of the EU; and
- Exports of ACP fishery products to the European market on preferential conditions under the Cotonou Agreement.

There are also other trade agreements that directly affect fisheries between South Africa and the rest of the World, namely the:⁷⁰

- **Southern African Customs Union** which allows for a duty free movement of goods with a common external tariff on goods entering any of the countries from outside the SACU;
- **Free Trade Agreements** which allows for reduced duties on certain category of products. There is currently a review of the agreement underway, which is

⁶⁷ McCord & Zweig (2011).

⁶⁸ UNCTAD (2012).

⁶⁹ CTA (2006).

⁷⁰ http://www.thedti.gov.za/trade_investment/ited_trade_agreement.jsp

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aimed at broadening the scope of product coverage between South Africa and the EU. This is taking place under the auspices of the Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA) negotiations between SADC and the EU.

- **European Free Trade Association-SACU Free Trade Agreement** which allows for reduced tariffs on industrial goods (including fish and other marine products) and processed agricultural products.
- **Non-reciprocal Trade Arrangements** such as the Africa Growth and Opportunity Act which grants 39 Sub-Saharan African countries preferential access to the US market through lower tariffs or no tariffs on some products.

3.4 KEY OVERARCHING POLICY FRAMEWORKS

3.4.1 *National Development Plan*⁷¹

By 2030, South Africa's rural communities are expected to have better opportunities to participate fully in the economic, social and political life of the country. The vision includes better integration of the country's rural areas, achieved through successful land reform, infrastructure development, agro-processing, job creation and poverty alleviation. The NDP identifies, among others, the core fundamental issues in the fisheries that need realistic and sustainable solutions. Transformation of the sector, fishing rights allocation and sustainable exploitation of fisheries resource is advocated in the NDP to be prioritised. In view of the fundamental issues, the NDP acknowledges that the fishing sector is relatively transformed, however, fishing activities are not inclusive. Furthermore, the NDP warns against issuing many fishing rights of low value because it lowers the average gain per fisher and could be ineffective in fighting poverty and non-compliance among fishers. With view of industrial fishing, the NDP is against taking fishing rights away from industrial fishers in favour of small-scale fishers because this would cut jobs.

Fisheries research and effective monitoring systems are considered as of paramount importance to ensure a viable and sustainable fishery. The NDP recommends that alternative economic opportunities need to be made to supplement livelihoods of fishing communities; and fisheries policies should seek to maximise sustainable employment and advocate for allocation of viable fishing rights. In response to the NDP, the Department and the Marine Living Resources Fund will support aquaculture production, create jobs through Working for Fisheries Programme, rebuild depleted fish stocks, and allocate commercial fishing rights to promote participation in the South African fisheries.

3.4.2 *Industrial Policy Action Plan*⁷²

South Africa's long-term vision of an equitable society is provided by the National Development Plan. The Industrial Policy Action Plan (IPAP), which is developed by the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), is informed by this vision and is both framed

⁷¹ National Planning Commission (2012).

⁷² Department of Trade and Industry (2014).

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by and constitutes a key pillar for the objectives set out in the NDP. The policy considerations driving the IPAP seeks to achieve diversification into non-traditional tradable goods and services, a labour-absorbing industrialisation path, increased participation of historically disadvantaged people, increased participation of marginalised regions and the long-term intensification of South Africa's industrialisation process and movement towards a knowledge economy. The plan identifies interventions which will lead to increased investment in the aquaculture sector and marketing of the growth of the aquaculture sub-sector of South Africa which in turn will lead to diversification of the sector, increased production and significant job creation. South African aquaculture has a potential to increase supply to the insatiable demand of fisheries products such as abalone, trout, mussels and oyster.

3.4.3 National Infrastructure Plan⁷³

The Presidential Infrastructure Coordinating Commission (PICC) was established with the aim of directing infrastructure development, a key job driver as identified by the NGP. From the spatial analysis of South Africa's needs, 17 Strategic Integrated Projects (SIPs) have been identified. The SIPs cover a range of economic and social infrastructure. Of relevance to agriculture, forestry and fisheries, is SIP 11: Agro-logistics and rural infrastructure. SIP 11, aims to improve investment in agricultural and rural infrastructure that supports expansion of production and employment, small-scale farming and rural development, including facilities for storage (fish storage and depuration facilities), transport links to main networks (rural roads, branch train-line, ports), improved research and development on rural issues (including expansion of colleges of agriculture), processing facilities (fish processing infrastructure), aquaculture incubation schemes and infrastructure in fishing harbours.

3.4.4 Medium Term Strategic Framework⁷⁴

Cabinet decided in 2013 that the 2014-2019 Medium Term Strategic Framework (MTSF) should form the first five-year implementation phase of the NDP and mandated work to begin on aligning the plans of national and provincial departments, municipalities and public entities with the NDP vision and goals. The Department contributes towards 3 (Outcome 4, 7 and 10) of the 14 priority Outcomes identified in the MTSF in response to the NDP. Some of the targets over the next five years under the three outcomes include:

- An increase in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate from 2.5 per cent in 2012 to 5 per cent in 2019
- Reduce rural unemployment from the current 49 per cent to less than 40 per cent
- Implementation of climate change responses in five critical sectors
- Increasing the percentage of the coastline with at least partial protection from 22.5 per cent in 2013 to 27 per cent in 2019

⁷³ PICC (2012).

⁷⁴ The Presidency (2014b).

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3.5 CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Over the past 5 decades, increased fishing pressure has resulted in the overexploitation and depletion of some fisheries resources. The once pristine marine and freshwater ecosystems have been degraded to an appalling state. Not all changes in fish stocks and ecosystems are due to sustained harvesting of the fisheries resources, but also climate change, habitat loss, invasive species and long-term natural fluctuations. However, there is a glimpse of hope as some of the implemented recovery strategies to limit overfishing and rebuild fish stocks are bearing positive results. Some environmental factors will still affect the fisheries and coastal economies now and well into the future. Carbon dioxide, for instance, the chief greenhouse gas (GHG) behind climate change, threatens the marine and freshwater ecosystems, thereby threatening the sustainability of the fishing industry and livelihoods of fishing communities.⁷⁵ The fishing sector is faced with many other challenges such as sensitivity and vulnerability to climate change, and extreme weather patterns, infrastructure and budget shortage, under-funded research and development, market and oil volatility, low and unstable fish stocks and other factors outside the control of the fishing industry.⁷⁶

South African fisheries faces numerous socio-political challenges that can be linked to the historical injustices that the country has been subjected to during the pre-democracy era. The democratic government realised that it cannot continue as business as usual in the skewed access to fisheries resources and introduced measures that were designed to usher in the transformation of the fishing sector. Central to this effort was the acknowledgement that fisheries resources belong to all South Africans and that there should be managed access to exploit the resources. Discussions led to the development of the White paper on Marine living resources, thereafter, the Marine Living Resources Act (MLRA), 1998 (Act 18 of 1998). The MLRA had its own weaknesses in the sense that as it was trying to be inclusive, it closed out some sector within the capture fisheries – the small-scale fisheries. It was the court order in favour of the small-scale fishers in 2007 that led to the initiation of the long processes to develop policy and legislative tools to formally recognise the small-scale fisheries sector. The small-scale fisheries policy (SSFP) was finalised in 2012, while the MLRA was formally recognised the small-scale fisheries sector in June 2014 after being signed into law. The implementation plan of the SSFP was approved by the Departmental executive and is expected to be implemented during the 2015/16 financial year. There are, however, real challenges such as the low, at times, depleted fish stocks in the inshore waters to be sustainably allocated to the small-scale fishers. Furthermore, allocation of fishing rights in the off-shore fisheries to small-scale fishers will require immense budget to industrialise the operations of small-scale fishers.

Up until the early 1990s, a change in policy of the provincial nature conservation departments resulted in a cessation of the production and stocking of exotic fish, to

⁷⁵ Department of Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries (2012b); FAO (2014b).

⁷⁶ Allison et al., (2009); Department of Environmental Affairs (2011).

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one of conserving South Africa's indigenous fish fauna. This constituted an effective withdrawal of Government support for the freshwater aquaculture industry, and resulted in the closure, or privatisation of many Government aquaculture facilities. The period of political transition in the early 1990s resulted in a lack of policy or funding to support aquaculture research and development, and without government support, the aquaculture industry in South Africa effectively developed at a much slower rate than in other parts of the world.⁷⁷ There is therefore a need to revamp or develop the infrastructure which was used for stocking exotic fish for aquaculture and pump financial resources to enable production. The newly established aquaculture incentive programme within the Department of Trade and Industry, the mobilisation of funds within the departmental programmes such as Comprehensive Agriculture Support Programme as well as funds availed by the Department of Rural Development and Land Reform created an enabling financial environment to invest in aquaculture.

Global fish demand on the increase, particularly in developed countries where their resources cannot meet the growing demand. Some developing countries are experiencing similar demand mainly due to imbalances in supply and demand. The global demand presents an opportunity to increase production where resources are still stable or under-exploited. The South African fishing industry, particularly, the aquaculture sector is gearing itself to exploit this opportunity.

The current state of fisheries resources does not require pressure being added to some limited resources, however there is a need for innovative ways to maximise profits on the available resources. This can be done through the development of policies that will encourage research and development in areas of secondary processing to produce value added products from the marine resources. For example, developing human consumable products from lower grade catches instead of directing the by-catch and substandard catch to fishmeal production. There is also a need for a comprehensive study on inland fisheries that will guide policy developments on any new fishery for the local economy and on food security. This will ensure that these developments do not impact negatively on those who draw benefits from recreational and subsistence fisheries. This policy will therefore guide decisions on resource allocation. However at present, the lack of a sound inland fisheries policy is a major stumbling block for sustainable inland fisheries development in South Africa. As a result, the economic potential of these water bodies is unknown.

The aquaculture projects which were led by provincial governments as a subsistence enterprise or for food security have proven unsuccessful. There is therefore a need for a different approach which should be small-scale commercial aquaculture. For this to be successful, policies will need to:⁷⁸

- to develop a framework to address the lack of support and services to farmers
- guide the develop of commercially orientated small scale aquaculture projects, instead of the "food security" type projects

⁷⁷ Rouhani & Britz, 2011

⁷⁸ Rouhani & Britz (2011).

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- encourage community-public-private partnerships to promote market linked small-scale aquaculture

3.6 RECOMMENDATIONS AND ROLE OF PARLIAMENT

There are at least seven issues that need to be raised by Parliament in that the Department will need to consider as it moves towards allocation of fishing rights that move away from conventional fishing towards wealth-based fishing.

- **Capacity-building:** this is a major requirement and will include (i) research (e.g. predictive bio-economic modelling approaches rather than a continued emphasis on backward-looking biological stock assessment); (ii) administration (e.g. to upgrade staff skills in fisheries management); (ii) industry (e.g. to improve organisation structure and function with reference to new co-management frameworks);
 - **Supporting the process:** experience from successful countries (e.g. Australia, Iceland, New Zealand) shows that the move towards commercial models is a lengthy process (decades in duration) and support to the fishery management process itself will be needed;
 - **Targeting micro-level assistance:** to help South Africa develop and implement plans around the wealth generation concept, assistance (financial, infrastructure and skilled human) will be required at local level, to complement the recent high level international initiatives aimed at improving fisheries governance;
 - **Stimulation of fish consumption:** there is a need to increase awareness and local demand on a variety of fish and fish products through better and targeted marketing;
 - **Building awareness and political support:** a new approach to wealth generation and use in fisheries will require high level political support. This must be underpinned by generating awareness, throughout society, of the potential wealth of fish resources
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4 MARKET SHARE OF THE TOURISM SECTOR

- Mr Abdullah Ganief

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism is an industry with great potential to foster development and create new employment opportunities in South Africa. Tourism has recently become a global economic phenomenon; it takes place in destinations across the world, from leading capital cities to small towns and from villages in rural and coastal areas to some of the remotest areas on the planet. From the year 2000, international arrivals worldwide rose from 675 million to 940 million in 2010.⁷⁹ Worldwide, international tourist arrivals grew by 5.0% in 2013 to reach 1,1 billion. The growth was mainly driven by developed markets where arrivals grew by 5.4% while emerging markets grew by 4.5%.⁸⁰ Tourism contributes trillions of dollars to the global economy, creating jobs and wealth, generating exports and boosting taxes. The industry provides over 260 million jobs around the world directly or indirectly and through other related sectors. In 2012, G20 heads of state recognised tourism as a driver of growth and development, as well as a sector that has the potential to spur global economic recovery.

South Africa has earmarked tourism as a key sector with excellent potential for growth: the government aims to increase tourism's contribution, both direct and indirectly, to the economy from the 2009 baseline of R189,4-billion (7.9% of GDP) to R499-billion by 2020.⁸¹ Tourism supports one in every 12 jobs in South Africa. The employment contribution of the tourism industry in the country is estimated to increase from 593,800 in 2011 to approximately 664,200 in 2015.⁸² The hosting of the Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) 2010 Soccer World Cup led to an increase in the number of foreign arrivals in the country and tourism expenditure. This is also reflected by the increase in Google searches for accommodations in the country by foreigners. Tourism as a resilient industry expected to continue to perform better as shown by the Tourism Business Index (TBI).

The amalgamation of the two large industries, agriculture and tourism, created a new industry called agritourism. Current farming practices in South Africa are not securing employment opportunities for farm workers, and this situation will be aggravated by the increased economic pressures on farming. Agritourism is seen as a diversification option which could assist in creating jobs for the vulnerable and unemployed farm community, while at the same time create financial incentives to the farmer. Agriculture can be seen as the most potent and enduring symbol of rurality, and it has been the dominant and driving force of rural economies for many centuries.⁸³ In the Rural Tourism Strategy compiled by the Department of Tourism (2011b:7), tourism and agriculture were identified as the potential economic pillars for rural development in

⁷⁹ World Travel & Tourism Council, 2011.

⁸⁰ World Travel & Tourism Council, 2011.

⁸¹ National Department of Tourism, 2012.

⁸² National Department of Tourism, 2012.

⁸³ Woods, 2005.

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South Africa. The aforementioned document further states that if more tourism can be developed in rural areas, the poverty in the areas can be alleviated.

One of the advantages of tourism is that developing countries can use tourism to generate foreign exchange, address employment challenges, attract development capital and strive to achieve economic independence.⁸⁴ Other advantages of tourism include economic impulses which will be created for the local communities, a greater awareness of the natural and cultural resources and the local people will have a stronger motivation to stay in the specific area and not to urbanise.⁸⁵ This statement is supported by the Rural Tourism Strategy compiled by the Department of Tourism which states that tourism has the capacity to provide an alternative to urbanisation, and rural tourism can permit people to continue a rural family existence.

Over and above the above mentioned advantages, further advantages of tourism include the entrepreneurial opportunities which are created by the industry, the development of infra and supra structure, the stimulation of other industries such as agriculture by tourism and it also helps to build national pride.⁸⁶ The above mentioned author also notes additional advantages such as preservation of heritage and traditions, appreciation for culture and traditions and broadening of education of tourist and host community.⁸⁷

4.2 TOURISM AS EMPLOYMENT CREATOR

The official unemployment rate in South Africa for the last quarter of 2011 was 23,9 percent, which is the highest level of unemployment from the 60 countries that have been tracked by Bloomberg news service.⁸⁸ According to Nel the official unemployment number for South Africa is approximately 40 percent, but figures of up to 80 percent have been recorded in some rural areas.⁸⁹ The Rural Tourism Strategy which has been compiled by the Department of Tourism states that between 10 and 15 million people in South Africa live in areas characterised by extreme poverty and underdevelopment. Creating jobs in South Africa is the single most important task, and it is central to government's objective to eliminate poverty by 2030.⁹⁰ The largest portion of the "working poor" is found in the rural areas, and proposes that if the national government wants to reduce unemployment to 6 percent by 2030, approximately 11 million more jobs need to be created and the portion of adults working in the rural areas will need to rise from the present 29 to 40 percent.⁹¹

⁸⁴ Telfer and Wall, 1996.

⁸⁵ Min and Cheng, 2011

⁸⁶ Saayman, 2007.

⁸⁷ Saayman, 2007.

⁸⁸ Anderson, 2012.

⁸⁹ Department of Tourism, 2011.

⁹⁰ Bimbassis, 2012.

⁹¹ Bimbassis, 2012.

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In the National Tourism Sector Strategy which has been compiled by the Department of Tourism, “tourism is seen as a multifaceted industry that contributes to a variety of economic sectors, but it is also a labour-intensive industry that has the capacity to create jobs”. In less developed and peripheral areas of Europe, tourism is seen as one of the main industries which provide employment opportunities⁹², and the researcher foresees a similar trend in South Africa through the implementation of various strategies for example the Rural Tourism Strategy and the National Tourism Sector Strategy which have been compiled by the National Department of Tourism. According to the Medium-Term Strategic Framework⁹³ tourism is perceived as a priority economic sector, and the priority to create decent work and sustainable livelihood has been acknowledged. The IPAP2 has identified tourism as one of the areas which is expected to contribute to the development of rural areas and culture by growing the economy and creating jobs.⁹⁴

Tourism creates three types of employment: direct employment for people who are directly employed in tourism facilities, indirect employment defined as the jobs that contribute to the tourism industry and induced employment in an area due to the economic upsurge which is caused by tourism.⁹⁵ The aforementioned author continues that tourism has become a part of the South African government’s strategy to alleviate poverty through job creation by focussing on Spatial Development Initiatives (SDI) in certain rural areas. SDI’s were supposed to facilitate economic growth through job creation and private investment in these areas.⁹⁶ President Zuma indicated that the government would like to create 235 000 new tourism jobs by 2020 and further reiterated that government is committed to achieving these developmental goals.⁹⁷

Tourism has the potential to create jobs and this is important since there have been significant job losses in recent years in South Africa.⁹⁸ One of the government’s main priorities is unemployment and has initiated a number of strategies to address this challenge that is impeding poverty alleviation. From above discussion, it is evident that the tourism industry can play an important role in creating job opportunities and directly influence a positive contribution to the national GDP, which will be discussed in the next section of this chapter.

4.3 TOURISM AS GDP GENERATOR

Researchers surmises that economic growth is measured by the changes in a country’s gross domestic products (GDP) where the domestic product consists of the total market value of all final goods and services produced within the boundaries of a country during

⁹² Hegarty and Przezborska, 2005.

⁹³ Hegarty and Przezborska, 2005.

⁹⁴ Department of Tourism, 2011

⁹⁵ Erlank, 2005.

⁹⁶ Erlank, 2005.

⁹⁷ Hartley, 2011.

⁹⁸ Binns and Nel, 2002.

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one year.⁹⁹ In the National Tourism Sector Strategy it states that tourism is perceived as one of the six core pillars of growth in the country. The other pillars are infrastructure development, the agricultural value chain, the mining value chain, the green economy and the manufacturing sectors, as stated in IPAP2.

According to the 2010 Tourism Satellite Account tourism directly contributed about R67 million equalling 3 per cent of the country's GDP.¹⁰⁰ The South African government aims to increase tourism's total contribution to the economy from R189 billion in 2009 to R499 billion by 2020.¹⁰¹ Unfortunately the tourism industry worldwide is currently affected by volatile exchange rates, an international economic crisis, high oil prices and fuel hedging costs and policy responses to climate change, all of which impacts the industry.¹⁰² These challenges may hamper the intended growth that the government aims to achieve.

The advantages of tourism are attractive as it's aimed to address poverty in South Africa, but unfortunately there are also some disadvantages for utilising tourism as a developmental tool. Tourism development has inherent disadvantages, and if these challenges are not addressed, it could be catastrophic for the entire industry.¹⁰³ The aforementioned author further states economic threats such as the seasonality of tourism, economic dependence, over development, importing of goods and services to adhere to tourist demand, rising property prices and the intense use of resources are just some of the disadvantages of tourism.¹⁰⁴

4.4 TRENDS AND CHANGES IN MARKETS

According to the PwC Hospitality Outlook Reports for 2013 and 2014 respectively, there was a relative increase in tourism in South Africa. The table below reflects tourism performance for year past 2013/14 including future estimates. The 2013 growth with regards to foreign overnight visits increase at a much lower rate than the previous 2012/3 at 3.7% from 10.2%. In the case of domestic travel, the increase by 2.4% came at the back of an over 8% decline the previous year.¹⁰⁵

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2014-18 CAGR
Foreign overnight visitors	6.39	6.75	7.01	8.07	8.34	9.19	9.53	9.90	10.30	10.75	11.20	11.70	
% change	8.1	5.6	3.9	15.1	3.3	10.2	3.7	3.9	4.0	4.4	4.2	4.5	4.2
Domestic travellers	4.45	4.42	4.49	5.13	5.43	4.97	5.09	5.22	5.36	5.52	5.70	5.90	
% change	3.0	-0.7	1.6	14.3	5.8	-8.5	2.4	2.6	2.7	3.0	3.3	3.5	3.0
Total	10.84	11.17	11.5	13.2	13.77	14.16	14.62	15.12	15.66	16.27	16.90	17.60	
% change	6.0	3.0	3.0	14.8	4.3	2.8	3.2	3.4	3.6	3.9	3.9	4.1	3.8

¹⁰² Department of Tourism, 2011.

¹⁰³ Saayman, 2007.

¹⁰⁴ Saayman, 2007.

¹⁰⁵ PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2014.

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Sources: Statistics South Africa, PricewaterhouseCoopers LLP, Wilkofsky Gruen Associates

The tourism growth in South Africa is against depressed global economic environment reflected in a lower than expected economic growth in South Africa. The World Bank Report 2013, and the South African Reserve Bank economic growth has been revised down wards to 1.4% instead of the reflected 1.9% below.¹⁰⁶

Real GDP growth (%)													
	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2014-18 CAGR
South Africa	5.5	3.6	-1.3	3.1	3.4	2.4	1.9	3.3	3.4	3.6	3.8	3.7	3.6
Global	5.4	2.8	-0.6	5.2	4.0	2.8	3.1	3.7	3.9	4.0	4.2	4.1	4.0

Sourced: PwC LLP Hospitality Outlook 2014

At an aggregated level, the growth in foreign visits per region is that; from Europe increased 5.4 %, North American visitors rose 5.6%, Latin America and Asia-Pacific Africa rose by 7.4% and 6.7%, respectively. Visits other countries in Africa totaled 6.9 million in 2013, up 3.3% from 2012 and accounting for 72% of the total number of foreign visitors to South Africa.¹⁰⁷

The following table represents the split of domestic and international visitors in a form of a graph.

Domestic and foreign visitors (millions)

Sources: Statistics South Africa, PricewaterhouseCoopers LLP, Wilkofsky Gruen Associates

¹⁰⁶ PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2014.

¹⁰⁷ PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2014.

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About a third of overnight visits into South Africa are on business, conferencing non-leisure travel. The growth the previous year, as illustrated in the table below, was much slower than the year before. PwC attributes the growth to the loss of former President Nelson Mandela and the African Nations Cup football at the beginning of the year in 2014. Essentially, the PwC argues that South Africa has continued to withstand the international trend of a declining tourism travel due to the difficult economic environment.

4.5 INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENTS

Nearly all WTO members emphasize the importance of tourism, especially in terms of its contribution to employment and generating foreign exchange. Typically one of the most dynamic economic sectors, tourism-related services are labour-intensive, with numerous links to other major segments of the economy. Tourism and travel-related services includes services provided by hotels and restaurants (including catering), travel agencies and tour operator services, tourist guide services and other related services.

One of the most crucial aspects of international tourism is the cross-border movement of consumers. This permits even unskilled workers in remote areas to become services exporters, for instance, by selling craft items, performing in cultural shows, or working in a tourism lodge. While back in 1950, the top 15 destinations absorbed 98 per cent of all international tourist arrivals, in 1970 the proportion was 75 per cent, and this fell to 57 per cent in 2007, reflecting the emergence of new destinations, many of them in developing countries.¹⁰⁸

Tourism commitments have been made by over 125 WTO members, more than in any other services sector. Tourism services are included in the new services negotiations, which began in January 2000. The principles of trade in tourism services are contained, as for all services, in the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS)¹⁰⁹.

4.6 KEY LEGISLATION AND POLICY FRAMEWORKS

National Government is the highest level of South Africa's political institutions, followed by provincial, district and then local governments. On the national level, there is numerous legislation which guides tourism development on local government level. This include:

¹⁰⁸ World Trade Organisation, 2014.

¹⁰⁹ The General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) mandates WTO member governments to progressively liberalize trade in services through successive rounds of negotiations. Under the mandate of Article XIX, the latest round of negotiations began in January 2000. In March 2001 the Guidelines and Procedures for the Negotiations on Trade in Services were adopted by the Council for Trade in Services. At the Doha Ministerial Conference in November 2001 the services negotiations became part of the "single undertaking" under the Doha Development Agenda, whereby all subjects under the negotiations are to be concluded at the same time.

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- The Constitution of South Africa, no 108 of 1996

The Constitution of South Africa specifies the roles of national, provincial and local governments and states the different roles that each government level has with respect to tourism development and management.

According to Section 152 of the Constitution, the objectives of local government are:

- To provide democratic and accountable government for local communities
 - To promote social and economic development
 - To encourage the involvement of communities and community Organisations in the matters pertaining to local government
- The White Paper on the Development and Promotion of Tourism in South Africa, 1996

This White Paper on tourism development promotes the development and management of the tourism industry in South Africa in a responsible and competitive manner. Key guiding principles for tourism development, as set out in the White Paper, follows:

- Development through tourism should be private sector driven
 - Government should provide an enabling environment for the development of tourism
 - Effective community involvement should form the basis of tourism growth
 - Tourism should be underpinned by sustainable environmental practices
 - Tourism development is dependent on co-operation and close partnerships among key stakeholders
 - Tourism should be used as a developmental tool for the empowerment of previously neglected communities
 - A safe and stable tourism environment should be created
- National Responsible Tourism Guidelines, 2002

The National Responsible Tourism Guidelines was published by the Department of Environmental Affairs and Tourism in 2002. According to these guidelines, responsible tourism development should be economically, environmentally and functionally sustainable. It is imperative that the responsible tourism guidelines be taken into account when planning for and developing tourism attractions and facilities.

Responsible Tourism Development should be regarded as the key guiding principle tourism development. The values that support this concept are indicated below:

- Responsible tourism development implies a proactive approach by relevant stakeholders to develop market and manage the tourism industry in a responsible manner, so as to create a competitive advantage.

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- The industry has a responsibility to the environment through the promotion of balanced and sustainable development is imperative, thus focussing on the promotion of environmentally based tourism activities.
 - Responsible tourism means that the government and businesses have a responsibility in terms of involving local communities in tourism thus creating income generating activities by which local communities will benefit.
 - Tourists, developers, government and the industry have a responsibility in terms of respecting, investing in and developing local cultures, also protecting them from over-commercialisation and over-exploitation.
 - A responsibility also exists in terms of ensuring the safety and security of visitors within a host community or the host country.
 - Responsible tourism development requires the responsibility of both employers and employees in the industry, both to one another, as well as to the customer.
- National Heritage Resources Act, no 107 of 1998

Some areas have a variety of heritage resources relating to anthropology, culture, archaeology, geology and bio-diversity. These resources can be utilised for the development of tourism products and attractions. Principles with regard to the management of heritage resources are included below:

- Heritage resources have the capacity to promote reconciliation, understand and respect and contribute to the development of a unifying South African identity.
 - Heritage resources contribute significantly to research, education and tourism and must be developed and presented for these purposes in a way that ensures dignity and respect for cultural values.
 - The integration of heritage resource conservation in urban and rural planning and social and economic development should be promoted.
 - Affected communities have a right to be consulted and to participate in management.
 - The skills and capacities of persons involved in the management of heritage resources should be developed and on-going education and training must be ensured.
- Environmental Acts

Various environmental acts in South Africa pertain to the development of tourism related activities. These include

- National Environmental Management Act, no 107 of 1998
 - National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, no 57 of 2003
- The New Growth Path, Tourism and Creative Industries

The macro-economic development strategy for South Africa, the New Growth Path (2011), identifies the tourism sector as a critical driver for job creation and highlighted the poverty reduction potential of the sector. This strategy recognised that tourism is a

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labour-intensive industry and puts forward the target of 225 000 additional jobs by the year 2020. Related to tourism destination development is the Department of Arts and Culture's approach to arts, culture and heritage that fits within the New Growth Plan in a manner that promotes social cohesion, skills development economic growth.

- The National Tourism Sector Strategy, 2011

The National Tourism Sector Strategy aims to grow sustainable tourism both in the domestic and international markets with a focus on innovation, service excellence and meaningful partnerships. Higher spending markets are targeted, as are increasing visitor numbers. Specific targets include attracting R35 billion more in public sector/government investment in tourism infrastructure and R1 billion more in international direct investment.

- Specific objectives outlined in the strategy include:
 - Grow tourism's contribution to the economy.
 - Provide excellent people development and decent work in the sector.
 - Increase domestic tourism's contribution to the tourism economy.
 - Contribute to the regional tourism economy.
 - Deliver world-class visitor experiences.
 - Extend tourism culture among South Africans.
 - Position South Africa globally as a recognised tourism destination brand.
 - Achieve transformation within the sector.
 - Address the issue of geographic, seasonal and rural spread.
 - Promote responsible tourism practices within the sector.
 - Unlock the tourism development potential at provincial and local government level.

- Domestic Tourism Growth Strategy, 2012-2020

South Africa's national Domestic Tourism Growth Strategy provides for the enhanced focus on domestic tourism since domestic tourism is an essential contributor to the growth of the tourism economy and provides a foundation for sustainable tourism growth and development, more especially in times of global uncertainties.

Strategic objectives set out by the strategy include:

- To increase domestic tourism revenue (expenditure)
- To increase domestic tourism volume
- To improve measures and efforts aimed at addressing seasonality and geographical spread
- To enhance the level of the culture of travel and tourism among South Africans

- National Heritage and Cultural Tourism Strategy

The vision of the strategy is to realise the global competitiveness of South African heritage and cultural resources through sustainable tourism product development. It

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points out that heritage and cultural tourism products are underrepresented in tourism marketing and that the value of this segment of tourism has not been fully realised in South Africa the strategy aims:

- To provide strategic guidance to support the integration and coordination of heritage and cultural resources into mainstream tourism for product development and sustainable tourism
 - To utilise heritage and cultural tourism products, through strategic partnerships and the participation of local communities, to stimulate sustainable livelihoods at community grass-roots levels
 - To provide an opportunity to raise awareness, increase education and profile the conservation needs of heritage and cultural resources for sustainable tourism which is in line with values of respect for culture and heritage
 - To provide an opportunity for the diversification of tourism products and the formalisation of the segment or niche of heritage and cultural tourism, towards contributing to the growth of tourism.
- National Rural Tourism Strategy

The National Department of Tourism (NDT) developed this strategy to ensure a developmental approach when packaging rural tourism products and opportunities in South Africa. The approach also prioritises spatial nodes which have growth potential to ensure growth in the tourism industry is stimulated. The strategy aims to address the following objectives:

- To create a platform to share knowledge of best practice, development opportunities and challenges in rural areas for tourism development
- To facilitate the coordination of rural tourism development initiatives amongst relevant stakeholders
- To create an enabling environment for rural tourism development to stimulate job creation;
- To identify and recommend strategic areas/nodes for tourism development in rural areas within the sector

To guide strategy development within key documentation generated for tourism development and management in South Africa

4.7 COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE RELATIVE TO OTHER TRADING PARTNERS

Destination competitiveness is determined by a range of factors. These consist of the variety of a destination's natural and cultural resources, and visitor services; as well as general infrastructure, the quality of service, accessibility, hospitality, market ties, innovation, and last but not least price.¹¹⁰

South Africa's ranking in the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index has decreased from 61st in 2009 to 66th in 2011. The country performed relatively well in terms of

¹¹⁰ Dwyer and Kim, 2010.

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natural resources, price competitiveness and travel infrastructure, but achieved lower scores for safety and security, health and hygiene, ICT, the availability of qualified labour, and cultural resource development.¹¹¹

In order for South Africa to maintain its current strengths while creating new attractions and experiences for repeat visitors and diverse markets, it is essential to ensuring on-going competitive advantages in the tourism industry. In light of the above profiles, South Africa's current competitors include:

- South America (specifically Brazil)
- Western Europe
- Australia
- Thailand
- The rest of South Africa (especially Gauteng, KZN and Mpumalanga)
- The rest of Africa (specifically Nairobi in Kenya, Cairo in Egypt, and Morocco)

Backpacker tourism is recommended as a key niche market with further development. Competitive markets for backpacking are South America, Australia and USA for backpacking.¹¹² These areas are well developed budget tourism infrastructures and price is of critical importance.

Key considerations in terms of ensuring that South Africa is competitive rests on price, value for money and quality. South Africa needs to be competitive with other popular tourism destinations in emerging markets such as Thailand, Malaysia, India, Brazil and Argentina. However, as a result of the FIFA World Cup prices have increased significantly in South Africa and business owners seem to be reluctant to lower prices post event. This is essential in a world economy which is still in recession. This can deter visitor and cause South Africa to be uncompetitive in terms of price. South Africa has a reputation of being a well-priced and affordable destination. South Africa is a long-haul destination and flight fares are high, visitor services at destination level should therefore remain affordable or the overall cost of a trip to South Africa will become too high and uncompetitive. Furthermore, as a long-haul destination, it is important to diversify offerings to encourage longer stays. In order to better tap the domestic and regional market, attractive offerings need to be developed and marketed for off-season times.

Tourism firms and the sector need to innovate to stay ahead in order to enhance its competitiveness. However, in South Africa the innovation capacity of firms is generally quite low and disconnected from the regional key value chains.¹¹³ Technology transfer; industry, university and government linkages; and access to venture capital also remain weak as. Weak industry-university linkages contribute to skills shortages

¹¹¹ WEF, 2011.

¹¹² Visser and Barker,2004.

¹¹³ OECD, 2008.

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experienced by the industry. Concerted attempts to foster coordination between the main stakeholders are required in order to promote innovation in the region.¹¹⁴

4.8 PUBLIC SECTOR SUPPORT

A further issue that needs to be addressed is the support the public sector provides to agritourism ventures. In the South African context, research state that the public sector of the country lack the knowledge, understanding and commitment to the tourism industry due to lack of capacity of local government, and this is constricting tourism development in rural areas.¹¹⁵ Research further argue that the role of the provincial tourism agencies are confined in the tourism policy document, but role incertitude, infighting and breakdown in communication and inter organisational relationship has been identified as fundamental limitation to proactive facilitation of tourism growth and development.¹¹⁶

Some of the risk factors which have been identified through research include limited knowledge of agritourism, low quality farm accommodation, lack of information about the requirements of guests, lack of time spent with guests, lack of finance to start the business, low levels of infrastructure and low levels of information about tourism activities and opportunities in areas, which summarise some of the challenges faced by the agritourism industry.¹¹⁷ The researcher suggests that many of these challenges can be addressed through better public sector support through better informed information centres in every town.

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¹¹⁴ OECD, 2008.

¹¹⁵ Briedenhann and Wickens, 2004.

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5 IMPACT OF WATER ON AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND TOURISM'S MARKET SHARE IN SOUTH AFRICA

- Mr T Manungufala

5.1 BACKGROUND

Water plays a role in all sectors of the economy and is essential in achieving sustainable development. The National Water Act, 1998 (Act No. 36 of 1998) (NWA) was promulgated to provide for fundamental reform of the law relating to water resources, recognising that water is a scarce and unevenly distributed national resource that belongs to all people. The NWA provides the Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS) with a mandate to protect, use, develop, conserve, manage and control South Africa's water resources in an integrated manner. Such integrated management of the resource depends inter alia on effective management of water quality, which in turn relies on managing both the resource and sources of pollution.¹¹⁸ The South African Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries and Tourism sectors are poised to contribute in a sustainable manner to rural development and poverty relief, and to large-scale economic development, diversification and export opportunities. The non-consumptive and integrated use of water for these sectors can be economically beneficial to the South Africa.

It is also important to classify the available water in terms of source and type, in order to show how much what there is in the world, refer to chart 1 below.

Chart 1 Distribution of Earth's water (source: Shiklomanov, 1993)

In the first bar (Earth's water), only 2.5 per cent of all Earth's water is freshwater, which is what life needs to survive. The middle bar (Freshwater) shows the breakdown on that 2.5 per cent which is freshwater. Almost all of it is locked up in ice and in the ground. Only a bit more than 1.2 per cent of all freshwater (which was only 2.5 per cent of all water) is surface water, which serves most of life's needs. The right side bar (Fresh surface water) shows the breakdown of only the surface freshwater, which was

¹¹⁸ Department of Water Affairs (1998).

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only about 1.2 per cent of all freshwater. Most of surface freshwater is locked up in ice, and another 20.9 per cent is in lakes. The 0.49 per cent of surface freshwater that is in rivers. Sounds like a tiny amount, but rivers are where humans get a large portion of their water from.

South Africa's economy is classified as a mixed economy, and it ranks second largest in Africa after Nigeria. It also has a relatively high GDP per capita compared to other countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (\$11,750 at PPP as of 2012). Despite this, South Africa is still burdened by a relatively high rate of poverty and unemployment, and is also ranked in the top 10 countries in the world for income inequality, measured by the Gini coefficient. Unlike most of the world's poor countries, South Africa does not have a thriving informal economy; according to OECD estimates, only 15 per cent of South African jobs are in the informal sector, compared with around half in Brazil and India and nearly three-quarters in Indonesia. The OECD attributes this difference to South Africa's widespread welfare system. World Bank research shows that South Africa has one of the widest gaps between per capita GNP versus its Human Development Index ranking, with only Botswana showing a larger gap.¹¹⁹

After 1994 government policy brought down inflation, stabilised public finances, and some foreign capital was attracted, however growth was still subpar. From 2004 onward economic growth picked up significantly; both employment and capital formation increased. South Africa is a popular tourist destination, and a substantial amount of revenue comes from tourism. Illegal immigrants are involved in informal trading. Many immigrants to South Africa continue to live in poor conditions, and the immigration policy has become increasingly restrictive since 1994.¹²⁰

Principal international trading partners of South Africa—besides other African countries—include Germany, the United States, China, Japan, the United Kingdom and Spain. The South African agricultural industry contributes around 10 per cent of formal employment, relatively low compared to other parts of Africa, as well as providing work for casual labourers and contributing around 2.6 per cent of GDP for the nation. Due to the aridity of the land, only 13.5 per cent can be used for crop production, and only 3 per cent is considered high potential land. In August 2013, South Africa was ranked as the top African Country of the Future by FDi Intelligence magazine based on the country's economic potential, labour environment, cost-effectiveness, infrastructure, business friendliness, and foreign direct investment Strategy. The Financial Secrecy Index (FSI) ranks South Africa as the 36th safest tax haven in the world, ahead of the Philippines but behind the Bahamas.¹²¹

The world runs on water. Clean, reliable water supplies are vital for industry, agriculture, tourism, fisheries and energy production. Every community and ecosystem on Earth depends on water for sanitation, hygiene, and daily survival. Yet the world's water systems face formidable threats. More than a billion people currently live in

¹¹⁹ Central Intelligence Agency (2015).

¹²⁰ The Economist (2010).

¹²¹ Walls J (2013).

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water-scarce regions, and as many as 3.5 billion could experience water scarcity by 2025. Increasing pollution degrades freshwater and coastal aquatic ecosystems. And climate change is poised to shift precipitation patterns and speed glacial melt, altering water supplies and intensifying floods and drought. The impact of all these events will ultimately rest with the sectors that depends on water.

Figure 1. Water Use by Sector¹²² (adapted)

Figure 1 shows the use of water by sector – Agriculture is the biggest consumer with 60 per cent while Municipal or Domestic use accounts for 27 percent. It can be concluded that Agriculture cannot optimally operate without water in general. Agriculture is water intensive and its market share is entirely dependent on the quality and quantity of water.

5.2 IMPACT OF WATER ON THE AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY, FISHERIES AND TOURISM'S MARKET SHARE

The contribution of water to these sectors could be positive or negative depending on the availability, quality and quantity of water. Since all sectors depends on water in one way of another – water can be a limiting factor. This section would provide illustrations on how water contributes to the market share of the aforementioned sectors. In in order to explicitly describe the economic impact of water on these sectors – relevant examples of the impact of drought in South Africa and the world would be used. Furthermore the uses of water would be explored into order to show how water is an integral part or component of other sectors.

Drought impacts are most eye-catching in the agricultural sector. Dried crops, abandoned farmland, and withered and yellow pastureland are the common signs of

¹²² South African Institute of Race Relations (2013).

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drought. Prolonged soil moisture deficits due to drought cause damage to crops and pastures. Crop failures and pasture losses are the primary direct economic impact of drought within the agricultural sector. Drought-induced production losses cause negative supply shocks, but the amount of incurred economic impacts and distribution of losses depends on the market structure and interaction between the supply and demand of agricultural products. Drought-induced losses are not completely borne by farmers; instead, a portion of the losses are passed on to consumers through increased prices. The higher the price increases, the more losses will be passed on to consumers. It is even possible that farmers are better off from the drought impacts, given that the price increases by a higher percentage than the supply decreases. Additionally, farmers purchasing crop insurance will get part of their losses compensated by insurance companies, and some eligible farmers may receive direct disaster aid from the government. The ultimate losses borne by farmers could be very different from the actual impacts caused by drought. It is a common mistake to equate farmers' income losses with the economic impacts of drought.

One way to measure the impact of a drought (water scarcity) is to look at changes in Gross National Product (GNP) or Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Over the last three decades, specific droughts have reduced GNP by at least one percent in countries in East Africa, Europe, North America, South America, South-Eastern Asia/Australia, Southern Asia, and West Africa.¹²³ Measures of GDP over time show that economic downturns often materialize after a drought. For example, in the year after the 1984 droughts in Sub-Saharan Africa, the GDP for Mali, Niger, and Ethiopia fell by 9 percent, 18 percent, and 7 percent, respectively. Zimbabwe's GDP declined 3 per cent after the 1983 drought.¹²⁴ Because most Sub-Saharan African economies are driven primarily by agriculture, the effects of meteorological droughts are direct and can be large. In such countries, a majority of the population is employed in agriculture or pastoralism, and the sector's cash crops contribute to foreign-exchange earnings. Thus, the ramifications of drought are extended throughout the economy. Zimbabwe faced enormous economic losses as a result of the 1982/83 drought, including US\$ 360 million in direct agricultural losses and US\$ 120 million in drought relief costs.¹²⁵ The agricultural losses were experienced by both rural and commercial farmers, as a lack of rains hampered the maize crop and shortage of irrigation water caused a sharp decline in commercial wheat production (one of Zimbabwe's most important export crops).

¹²³ World Conference on Disaster Reduction (1994).

¹²⁴ Benson and Clay (1994).

¹²⁵ Ogallo, (1987).

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Chart 2 Economic Impact of Drought

The economic impact of drought is well documented – chart 2 shows exactly what happens when there is not enough water in a country – everything goes down from industrial output to consumption. This further illustrates how important water is to all sectors.

The definition of a drought for Kenhardt in the Karoo will differ from that of Knysna near the sea. The most common definition is that a drought occurs when the rainfall for a specific region is lower than the normal rainfall for a substantial period, usually measured over one year, causing a shortage in water and moist supplies. Whatever the definition of a drought, it is clear that it is not just a physical phenomenon but also an economical experience. South Africa experienced a drought between 2003 and early 2005, according to the definition. Rainfall for the calendar year of 2003 was below normal and this trend continued into 2004. The rainfall outlook for 2005 was also not very positive. The results in comparing 2004 with 2003 are visible in several ways: The yield of wheat was 39% lower; the area planted with summer crops were 12% lower; the water levels of the major dams was 25% lower; Several dams on farms were completely empty; and the available grazing pastures were about 30% of their normal capacity.¹²⁶

¹²⁶ Computus Management Information (2004).

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The economic impact of droughts on cash crops can be illustrated by examples of the maize and wheat crops. Graph 1 contains information for a number of years of the national plantings and also shows when long lasting droughts prevailed in South Africa.

Source: Computus Management Information (2004).

According to Graph 1, the droughts of 1966/68 and 1982/84, the areas planted for both wheat and maize remained quite constant. However, during the droughts of 1989/90 and 2003/04 the areas planted reduced substantially. The available moist during the planting period could have played a role in the areas planted. It could have been that enough rainfall occurred during the planting periods of 1966/68 and 1982/84 and that the drought had a delayed impact during the growing season. The opposite can be true for the two other droughts.

Source: Computus Management Information (2004)

The impact of droughts eventually reflects in yields (tons/hectare). Graph 3 contains information on the yields of wheat and maize for the past forty years. The yield (tons/hectare) for both wheat and maize decreased sharply during droughts. The exception was the maize crop of 2003/04 when late rain during the autumn caused a record crop in spite of smaller areas being planted. Once again, the inconsistency of maize also appears in the yield, also outside long lasting droughts. With the exception of 2003/04, the wheat yield is more consistent, even during droughts. In terms of area planted, crop size and yield, the wheat crop was extensively damaged by the drought of 2003/04. The smaller area planted under maize was countered by the exceptional good yield for the same period. It is also worth mentioning that the yields for both wheat and maize increased noticeably over the past forty years while the areas planted decreased. This is an indication that technology, in the form of cultivars and farming practices equipped the farmer to handle the consequences of the droughts better as

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far as yields are concerned than was the case twenty years ago. The yield of maize remains unsteady, in spite of the increasing yields. The normally consistent wheat crop suffered a serious blow during 2003/04 when the area planted, the crop size and not even the yield had any resistance to the drought.

The economic impact of a drought unfortunately doesn't stop with the loss of income experienced by the farmer. Although it causes an enormous impact on the individual farmer's financial resources, it also cycles out to the local economy of which the farmer is part. The table contains information about the spending of farmers regarding wheat and maize.

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Hectares	MAIZE		WHEAT	
	1	230	1	430
Yield	3.5 t/ha	3.5 t/ha	2.5 t/ha	2.5 t/ha
Expenses	R/ha	R	R/ha	R
Seed	R 333	R 76,590	R 152	R 65,360
Fertilizer	R 610	R 140,300	R 492	R 211,560
Weed control	R 178	R 40,940	R 56	R 24,080
Pest control	R 175	R 40,250	R 120	R 51,600
Crop spraying	R -	R -	R 99	R 42,570
Contract harvesting	R 247	R 56,810	R 304	R 130,720
Crop insurance	R 120	R 27,600	R 592	R 254,560
Transport	R 111	R 25,530	R 80	R 34,400
Fuel	R 177	R 40,710	R 205	R 88,150
Repairs & maintenance	R 696	R 160,080	R 573	R 246,390
Labour	R 76	R 17,480	R 61	R 26,230
Interest	R 85	R 19,550	R 67	R 28,810
TOTAL	R 2,808	R 645,840	R 2,801	R 1,204,430

Table 1. Spending on expense for Maize and Wheat Source: Computus Management Information (2004)

The table shows that an estimated R2,808 per hectare are being spend by farmers to produce maize while the expenses for wheat is slightly less at R2,801 per hectare. According to the financial results of farmers in the Eastern Free State participating in a study group of COMPUTUS, the average farmer cultivates 230 hectares of maize and 430 hectares of wheat per annum. The average farmer in the Eastern Free State therefore spends a total amount of R645, 840 on maize expenses and R1, 204.340 on wheat expenses in various ways in his local economy. The reducing of areas planted and the lower yields normally means that the farmer will spend less money in the succeeding year after a drought. A drought therefore causes a multiplying effect that has a huge influence in the economy of the local town. In this way a drought eventually has a huge negative impact on the total economy of the country, hence reduced market share of the sector concerned.

Nursery and landscaping service businesses also face big losses from drought. Droughts cause damage to nursery crops and add additional costs of watering newly installed plants and replacing dead ones. Plant sales may decline because of increased plant mortality and water use restrictions triggered by drought. During the historic drought in the southeast United States in 2007, many businesses were forced to close locations, lay off employees, or even file for bankruptcy. The Georgia-based nursery chain Pike Nursery filed for bankruptcy protection because of drought-induced financial difficulties. Other sectors subject to drought impacts include navigation and construction. Because the factors influencing business operations are numerous, drought impacts in non-agricultural sectors are uncertain and vary across time and

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location. It is important to consider the macroeconomic influences and local characteristics when estimating these impacts.

In the tourism and recreation sector, since many activities are water-related, droughts can bring critical losses to businesses in drought-stricken areas. Drought impacts exist for both winter and summer recreational activities. In winter, a lack of precipitation in the form of snow affects the business of ski resorts. Although many resorts could lessen the drought impact temporarily with snowmaking, it incurs additional costs and competition over water rights. Additionally, winter drought affects the level of snow pack stored at higher elevations, which in turn affects snowmelt and stream-flows during the following spring. Reduced stream-flows might result in fewer visits and a shorter rafting season. Other summer recreational activities, like fishing and boating, can be affected by drought as well, especially a multi-year drought that depletes water in lakes and reservoirs.

Tourism increases global water consumption, direct tourism-related water use is considerably less than 1 per cent of global consumption, and will not become significant even if the sector continues to grow at anticipated rates of around 4 per cent per year (international tourist arrivals). The situation differs at the regional level because tourism concentrates traveller flows in time and space, and often in dry destinations where water resources are limited. Furthermore, the understanding of tourism's indirect water requirements, including the production of food, building materials and energy, remains inadequately understood, but is likely to be more substantial than direct water use.¹²⁷

In comparison to other economic sectors, such as agriculture, there are no specific regional or national water use statistics for tourism, and tourism-related water use is still relatively little investigated. The following sections provide figures for direct (accommodation, activities) and indirect water use (fossil fuel use for transports, food, infrastructure), as these are available in the literature.

The existing literature suggests water consumption rates in a range between 84 to 2,000 L per tourist per day, or up to 3,423 L per bedroom per day (table 2). A considerable share of these volumes can be staff related, with for instance Lamei *et al*¹²⁸ reporting use values of 250 L per day per person in staff housing and 30 L per day for each staff during working hours. Overall, there is a tendency for higher standard accommodation to consume significantly higher water volumes, with for instance Bohdanowicz and Martinac¹²⁹ finding highest water use rates in hotels with spas and multiple and large swimming pools. Water-intensive facilities typically have landscaped grounds, requiring irrigation. Higher laundry volumes per guest per day are a result of sport and health centres, as well as affected by textile quality and/or weight of laundry items, including for instance very large towels at spa facilities. On global average, it has been suggested that an international tourist consumes 222 L per day.

¹²⁷ Gossling et al (2011).

¹²⁸ Lamei, A., Tilmant, A., van der Zaag, P., and Imam, (2009).

¹²⁹ Bohdanowicz and Martinac, (2007).

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With regard to water use categories and -shares, various factors seem to influence water use, including the geographical location of accommodation establishments (climate zone, urban-rural) as well as the hotel structure (high-rise, resort style) and comfort standard (e.g. campsite, 1-5-star hotel). According to one study of hotels in a tropical environment (Zanzibar, Tanzania), most water in hotels was used for continuous irrigation of gardens (50 per cent, or a weighted average of 465 L per tourist per day), a result of the poor storage capacity of the soils, high evaporation, and plant species not adapted to arid conditions. Vice versa, in guesthouses, the second dominant accommodation category, irrigation accounted for only 15 per cent of the total water use (37 L per tourist per day). The major proportion of water in guesthouses was spent for direct uses including taking showers, flushing the toilet, and the use of tap water (55 per cent, 136 L per tourist per day), with a corresponding consumption of 20 per cent or 186 L per tourist per day in hotels. The higher demand of hotel guests was found to be a result of additional showers taken at pools, and more luxurious bathroom facilities. Swimming pools represented another important factor of water use, accounting for about 15 per cent of the water demand of hotels (140 L per tourist per day). Indirectly, swimming pools added to laundry, for example when additional towels were handed out to guests. Guesthouses in the study area did not have swimming pools, which can partially explain lower water use rates. Laundry accounts for about 10 per cent (25 L per tourist per day) of the water used in guesthouses and 5 per cent (47 L per tourist per day) in hotels. Cleaning adds 5 per cent to the water demand in both guesthouses (12 L per tourist per day) and hotels (47 L per tourist per day). Finally, restaurants in guesthouses account for 15 per cent of the water used in guesthouses (37 L per tourist per day) and for 5 per cent (47 L per tourist per day) in hotels.¹³⁰

Considerably different results were presented by Smith *et al* for hotels in Australia, where major areas of water usage occurred in guest rooms (42 per cent), followed by kitchens (16 per cent), laundry (15 per cent), public toilets (12 per cent), cooling towers (10 per cent), irrigation (3 per cent) and swimming pools (2 per cent; no absolute water use figures presented). Yet another study of two hotels in Seattle, USA identified kitchens and public areas as the major factor in water use, followed by guest showers, guest toilets, laundry, leaks, cooling towers, guest floor ice and guest sinks.¹³¹ Finally, a study of water use in the Iberotel Sarigeme Park hotel in Turkey found that kitchen and laundry together constituted the largest water use (30 per cent), followed by swimming pools (20-25 per cent), and guest rooms (12 per cent)¹³²

Considerable amounts of water are also embodied in food consumption. UNESCO¹³³ (2009) reports, for instance, that depending on local climate, crop varieties and agricultural practices, it takes 400-2,000 L of water to produce 1 kg of wheat or 1,000 to 20,000 L of water to produce one kg of meat, depending on animal, feed and management. Based on these figures, it is estimated that daily water requirements to support human diets range from 2,000 to 5,000 L of water per person per day, with an estimate of 1 L of water for 1 kcal of food. Of importance in the context of tourism is

¹³⁰ Gössling, (2001).

¹³¹ O'Neill & Siegelbaum and The RICE Group (2002).

¹³² *Ibid.*

¹³³ UNESCO (2009).

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the fact that tourists may consume a greater share of higher-order, protein-rich foods with greater water footprints, while also requiring additional energy for transport by air over large distances, for instance in the case of small islands. In conclusion, a 14-day holiday may involve water use for food exceeding 70 m³ of water.¹³⁴

5.3 CONCLUSIONS

Water is an integral part of the Agriculture, Fisheries, Forestry and Tourism sectors in so far as their operations, process and development are concerned. Their market share depends on water to a large extent.

Agriculture is the major consumer of water in South Africa and in the world. As such if water diminishes in quality and quantity the Agricultural sector will shrink and ultimately cease to exist. The type of Agricultural activity that seems to be water intensive is the irrigation. Apart from irrigation livestock farming is also dependent on water – all agricultural activities are indirectly and directly linked to water consumption.

Tourism sector is also directly and indirectly dependent on water irrespective of type. For instance game farming which is used for recreational hunting. The wildlife would require water for drinking and the tourist would also need water to bath, drink, cook and cleaning – all these activities are directly dependent on water as such availability of water determines the size and magnitude of the tourism's market share.

In conclusion water is the life blood of all other sectors in that without it they cannot operate optimally. Therefore sustainable management of water in terms of use and development should always be a priority in the operation and development of all these other sectors to ensure sustainable development.

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¹³⁴ Gössling, Garrod, Aall, Hille and Peeters (2010).

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